

D7.2: XR Stakeholder's needs, requirements, and experiences from an ethics perspective

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1 Introduction

This report is the second of four deliverables of work package 7 (WP7). The main goal of WP7 is to guide and equip XR stakeholders through a rating system and an educational toolbox for informed decision making about XR. In Task 7.1, the first task in WP7, we consolidated the current state of the art of XR ethics practices in research and industry through systematic and scoping literature reviews (D7.1), as well as technology reviews of current XR solutions, both software and hardware. Task 7.2 focuses on the elicitation of needs, requirements and experiences from the stakeholders related to XR ethics aspects. For this purpose, we have refreshed the state of the art with latest XR efforts including ethics and designed an online survey to gather requirements from stakeholders. These requirements are then analyzed, prioritized, and will be finalized in Task 7.4, together with the online knowledge management tool, that is currently being developed as part of WP4.2 deliverable.

This report is structured in three parts.

Section 2 describes the methods for designing a structured online survey to elicit the needs, requirements, and experiences from the stakeholders.

Section 3 provides the results from the survey with analysis and prioritized requirements of XR ethics aspects from stakeholders.

Section 4 describes the initial efforts for presenting the insights from T7.2 using the online knowledge sharing tool, being developed in WP4.

2 Methodology

The main objective of Task 7.2 is to elicit ethics needs, requirements, and experiences with XR solutions. The methodology selected for this purpose is a structured online survey aligned with findings and recommendations provided in a variety of recent XR ethics reports, detailed hereafter. A structured online survey offers various advantages such as accessibility, cost-efficiency, rapid data collection, scalability, quantitative and qualitative analytical benefits. Moreover, it was considered that a dedicated survey in Task 7.2 would refresh and consolidate current XR ethics insights.

2.1 Survey Design

Ethics related findings from a variety of documents (XR4Human released reports, EU projects and citizen panels reports) were consolidated and used for selecting the most relevant themes and defining the survey questions. The available XR4Human deliverables as well as other EU initiatives and projects reports were used to this end.

Stakeholder analysis, stakeholder profiles and personas identified in D1.1 were used in the survey. The main ethics dimensions that are data & use of technology, human rights, and society, economy, and environment, identified in XR4Human D2.1 provided the three main thematic categories for the survey. Social and regulatory challenges, as well as regulations identified in D3.1 were also integrated in the survey. WP6 has already used dedicated surveys for dealing with XR use cases, good practices, and user experiences. Therefore, for the sake of avoiding redundancies, the survey in T7.2 did not consider these aspects specifically. However, these aspects will be harmonized in T7.4.

TechEthos D2.2 report (Adomaitis, 2022) provides core ethics dilemmas, as well as values and principles in XR. Some of these were used to some extent in the survey. Ethics considerations of extended reality provided by IEEE in seven different reports (McGill, 2021; Eriksson, 2021; Cortese et al., 2021;

Magnina, 2021; Evans, 2022; Fox et al., 2022; Middleton, 2022), as well as the findings and recommendations provided in the Final Report of European Citizens' Panel of Virtual Worlds (EU, 2023) were very useful in the survey design. Complementing the EU Citizens' Panel of Virtual Worlds, EU opportunities and challenges for next generation virtual worlds (Torres et al., 2023) were also considered during the survey design.

In addition to consolidating the survey with the above reports, ethics related issues were also discussed during two workshops with a total of around 20 participants at the Immersive Tech Week 2023.

2.1.1 Stakeholder categories

D1.1 identified personas of the main stakeholders and split them into 4 broad categories: policy makers, non-profit organizations (association, foundation, social organizations, etc.), companies (all types of businesses, XR users or non-users), and general public (XR users or non-users). Within these 4 broad categories 13 stakeholder groups were proposed as follows:

1. Industry and Developer Associations
2. Consumer Associations
3. Civil Society Organizations
4. General Public
5. Research Policy Makers
6. Legal Experts
7. Content Developers
8. Members of Research Ethics Councils
9. Science Journalists
10. General Public Users
11. XR Technology Developers
12. XR Technology Researchers
13. XR Technology Users

Within these stakeholder groups, different roles of the XR technology users are classified as technical, managerial, administrative, research, student, and general public.

2.1.2 XR Ethics Issues

The survey questions related to ethics were formulated based on the XR ethical issues identified in WP2. In D2.1, three thematic categories were identified as following:

Data and use of technology focus on ethical considerations related to the collection, storage, analysis, and use of data within immersive technologies. These cover issues such as data privacy, consent, security, and potential biases in XR data usage.

Human rights concerns address the ethical implications of immersive technologies for human rights. They include concerns related to topics such as autonomy, privacy, safety, freedom of expression, and the potential for discrimination or surveillance.

Societal, Economic, and Environmental concerns address the broader societal, economic, and environmental impacts of immersive technologies. They cover topics such as social inequality, economic disparities, environmental sustainability, and the potential for job displacement or economic disruption.

Based on above identified stakeholder categories, roles, and ethics issues in XR, the survey was created comprising 38 questions including 7 demographic questions, 19 XR ethics related questions with Likert-like rating scales and 11 open ended complementary questions for optional examples, enabling to gather participants' thoughts and experiences with the various topics.

The survey was initially distributed to the XR4human consortium for piloting and based on the feedback and inputs from the members, the questions were revised. An overview of the final survey structure is provided in Figure 1.

Aligned with GDPR requirements and to provide the context, motivation and purpose of the survey, an introduction section was added to the survey. In the introduction, the survey has a short description of the XR4Human project, goal of the survey, information about how the data will be stored and used for research. The survey was voluntary, and all participants provided informed consent before starting the survey. The participants were asked to provide demographic information (age group, gender, country of residence) followed by questions related to XR ethics with concerns categorized into data and use of technology; human rights; societal, economic, and environmental (SE&E) issues.

Figure 1: Structure of the final XR ethics survey.

2.1 Distribution of the survey

The survey was first published online in November 2023. Microsoft Forms was used as the survey tool and the survey has a dedicated weblink and QR-code for access. The survey was distributed to participants across various domains personally, at workshops (Immersive Tech Week 2023), via professional networking (LinkedIn posts, XRCrowd, XR4Europe, Stereopsia, Helsinki XR Center, XR Women, VRDays Foundation, Women in Immersive Technologies EU, Engage XR, VR for Health, etc.), as well as internal advertising at IFE on the information displays.

2.2 Data security and privacy

Microsoft Forms is part of the applications package in Microsoft SharePoint and is compliant with General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Necessary measures were taken to protect the privacy and security of the participants. All data from the survey were securely stored in the IFE's (the institution responsible for the work package and survey) dedicated database and access restricted only to the researchers associated with the XR4Human project and work package.

Since no sensitive information was collected in the survey, it was deemed not necessary to get approval from Sikt, the Norwegian Agency for Shared Services in Education and Research. It was optional for the participants in the survey to provide their email address for follow-up studies. These email addresses were stripped from the dataset before analyzing the data to ensure full anonymity. Participants were also provided with the contact information of the lead researcher of the survey team (lucas.stephane@ife.no) and the contact form to the XR4Human consortium (<https://xr4human.eu/#contact>) for any further clarification related to the survey and the project.

2.3 Data analysis

The collected survey responses were cleaned and prepared for thorough analysis to elicit relevant insights and support XR ethics efforts. Both quantitative and qualitative methods were utilised for the analysis. For summarising the demographic responses percentages and visualisations through charts and word clouds were used. For the responses to Likert-like scale questions descriptive statistics such as mean, median, standard deviations were calculated using MS excel to summarize the key characteristics of the responses. For the open ended-survey questions, qualitative analysis techniques such as text and content analysis were performed using generative Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools. The rationale behind using generative AI tools for qualitative analysis is further discussed in the results section.

3 Survey Results

A total of 112 responses were collected in the online survey and analyzed during the reporting period.

Multiple choices were allowed for the stakeholder category question: 28% of the respondents identified themselves as general public, 27% as XR solutions researchers, 25% as XR solutions developers, 23% as industry and developer associations, 19% content developers and 18% as XR solutions users. All categories provided in the list had at least one response while it is interesting to note that 18% of respondents identified themselves as 'other', outside the proposed stakeholder categories. Figure 2. provides a detailed overview of responses related to the stakeholder categories.

For the participants' involvement in XR question, multiple choices were allowed. In terms of their involvement or their roles in XR, 49% were researchers, 34% were technical involvement, followed by 30% general public, 26% with managerial involvement, and 15% that belong to the 'other' category, outside the roles proposed in the survey. Figure 3. summarizes the responses to participants' involvement in XR.

Industry and Developer Associat...	26
Consumer Associations	2
Civil Society Organizations	7
General Public	31
Research Policy Makers	11
Legal Experts	2
Content Developers	21
Members of Research Ethics Co...	5
Science Journalists	2
General Public Users	17
XR Solutions Developers	28
XR Solutions Researchers	30
XR Solutions Users	20
Other	20

Figure 2: Stakeholder category - responses

Technical	38
Managerial	29
Administrative	6
Research	55
Student	9
General public	34
Other	17

Figure 3. Participant's involvement in XR

3.1 Participant demographics

Most of the survey respondents were male (69%, 28% females). This is comparable with the gender ratios from other similar surveys in the project and likely reflects the demographics of individuals engaged in XR and broader technology sectors. Half of the survey respondents (47%) were between the ages of 35 to 54 years followed by 36% between 18 to 34 years, and 14% above 54 years old (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Gender & Age distribution of respondents

People from 23 countries participated in the survey, of which 70% were European (N=78). Of the 29% that were non-European (N=33) 23% were North American, 4% Asian and 2% South American. Country wise, 27% were from Norway, 20% from the USA, 6% from Belgium, 5% from the Netherlands, 4% each from France and Germany, 3.6% each from United Kingdom, Slovakia, Portugal, and Finland followed by small effectives from Spain, Canada, India, Brazil, Saudi Arabia, Greece, Latvia, Ukraine, Austria, Italy, Ireland, Trinidad & Tobago and UAE. The countries of all participants are summarized in the word cloud in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Word cloud representing countries of the respondents.

3.2 Analysis of results

3.2.1 Quantitative analysis

Since Microsoft Forms does not allow to start the numbering at 0, but only at 1, the questions were presented to participants on scales from 1 to 6, 1 corresponding to 'do not know', 2 corresponding to 'low', and 6 corresponding to 'very high'. For the statistical analysis, the scales were translated to 0 to 5 with equal weight. The 'do not know' responses are also provided for each rating scale.

Indeed, some questions have a very high number of ‘do not know’ responses that could indicate that there is a general lack of awareness, experience, or relationship of the topic with XR ethics among the participants.

Table 1 shows the ratings of the questions sorted in descending order. **N=112, values & means from 0 to 5, as well as the ‘do not know’ count**

Category	Question	Rating	Do not know #
Data & Tech Use	Q10 explicit consent	4.35	5
Data & Tech Use	Q8 privacy personally	4.27	3
Data & Tech Use	Q9 privacy professionally	4.22	3
Human Rights	Q31 need for ethical guidelines	3.76	5
SE&E	Q36 consider SE&E	3.63	7
Human Rights	Q14 diversity equity inclusion	3.61	5
Data & Tech Use	Q17 generative AI impacts	3.50	9
SE&E	Q34 disrupt traditional jobs	3.23	6
Data & Tech Use	Q15 avatars manipulation & misrepresentation	3.09	11
Human Rights	Q27 infringement on privacy & freedom of expression	3.04	10
SE&E	Q32 social inequality	2.77	13
Human Rights	Q25 autonomy & freedom impacts	2.72	15
Human Rights	Q12 exclusion of certain groups	2.14	33
Data & Tech Use	Q23 ethics awareness standards & best practices	2.12	20
Data & Tech Use	Q19 security concerns	2.06	32
Data & Tech Use	Q24 confident that regulations protect user data	1.75	18
Human Rights	Q11 lack of equal representation	1.72	42
Data & Tech Use	Q21 ethical issues related to data use	1.61	33
Human Rights	Q29 human rights concerns	1.28	51

Table 1: Three main XR ethics categories, and responses to questions sorted in descending order by their rating

For better understanding of participant’s confidence based on their average ratings per question, it was considered insightful to group the ratings in to three levels as follows: high (from 5 to 3.34), medium (from 3.33 to 1.67) and low (from 1.66 to 0).

The mean for ‘Do not know’ responses for the rating questions is 16.9 with a high standard deviation (14.41) showing a significant spread in the ‘Do not know’ responses among the questions. This could mean that the questions and ratings in the high category seem very clear to the participants. In the low category, participants did not seem to have encountered cases where XR solutions raised ethical concerns.

In the middle category, the medium ratings may come from the fact that some of the questions are related to future effects (e.g., Q25, Q32). Furthermore, the medium rating of Q23 provides a clear insight that participants are not aware of ethics standards for XR data usage, and Q24 provides a clear insight that participants do not think that current regulations protect user data in the context of XR solutions.

The last survey question addresses where participants seek XR ethics related information. The results show that 45% of participants are asking people they know, 43% consult online ethics websites, 35% address themselves to internal organizational resources, and 34% use online XR forums, 18% use “other” resources not listed in the survey categories, and 17% consult ethics specialized third party entities.

Figure 6: Responses to question 38 (Ethics-related information seeking)

3.2.2 Qualitative analysis

Participants were asked to optionally provide examples for 11 questions, complementing the related rating questions. The open feedback questions are presented in Table 2 sorted in descending order by the number of responses. The textual feedback gives interesting insight and complements the responses to the stakeholders’ rating questions, and the number of responses per question may indicate to some extent the interest of participants in the question. It is also interesting to notice that respondents provided a good amount of feedback even to questions toward the end of the survey, showing their engagement with questions they considered of interest (e.g., Q33 and Q35).

Category	Question	# Responses
Human Rights	Q13 equal representation or exclusion in XR	41
Data & Tech Use	Q18 generative AI impacts	37
SE&E	Q33 social inequality	35
Data & Tech Use	Q16 manipulation and misrepresentation using avatars in XR	34
SE&E	Q35 disrupt traditional jobs	32
Human Rights	Q26 autonomy & freedom impacts	28
Data & Tech Use	Q20 security concerns	26
SE&E	Q37 XR disruptions and impacts on society, economy, and environment	21
Human Rights	Q28 infringement on privacy & freedom of expression	21
Data & Tech Use	Q22 ethical issues related to data use	21
Human Rights	Q30 human rights concerns	14

Table 2: Open feedback questions categorized and sorted in descending order by the number of responses

Traditional text analysis performed by humans involves removing redundancies, extracting the main concepts, categorizing and synthesizing the textual feedback. The recent emergence of the use of generative artificial intelligence for text processing, exemplified by platforms like OpenAI’s ChatGPT, Google Gemini, and Perplexity AI, alongside the incorporation of AI capabilities into traditional qualitative analysis tools such as Atlas.ti (which uses OpenAI), NVivo and MAXQDA, has prompted the research team

to explore the potential of AI for analyzing the text feedback, specifically from the perspective of human-AI collaboration. This is an emerging field of research as recently more and more qualitative analyses are leveraging generative large language models (LLMs) for text analysis (De Kok, T., 2023). A recent study by Rathje and colleagues have found that GPT performs as well as and sometimes better than traditional methods at detecting psychological constructs in a text analysis (Rathje et al., 2023).

An initial comparison of results between Google Gemini and the free version of OpenAI ChatGPT was performed using the same prompt. The research team opted to use OpenAI ChatGPT, finding its detailed output more beneficial than the more synthesized shorter outputs from Google Gemini. Finally, for processing the open feedback for each question and the 26 pages of overall feedback, the paid version of ChatGPT 4.0 was employed.

The ChatGPT 4.0 synthesis of participants' feedback is provided hereafter, using the same prompt "extract the main user requirements and prioritize them based on occurrences from the following text:" followed by either each question text and the textual feedback provided by participants, or by the overall 26 pages of open feedback (Appendix 1). In some cases, it was necessary to clean and translate the feedback to English.

At this stage, the research team intended to keep control over the AI outputs, and therefore it was considered that processing participants' responses for each of the feedback questions (Appendix 2) would better enable the research team to understand and validate what was proposed by the AI tools, rather than working with large bodies of text from the start.

In a second stage, synthesis of all questions was generated and validated by the research team. This cumulated synthesis was compared with the AI generated synthesis of the overall raw participants' feedback (Appendix 3) and found more elaborated and usable.

Overall feedback synthesized from all processed questions

Based on the text provided, the main user requirements for XR (Extended Reality) can be extracted and prioritized as follows, based on their occurrences and the emphasis placed on each within the provided text:

1. **Economic and Geographic Accessibility:** This is highlighted as the most frequently mentioned user requirement, emphasizing the high cost of devices and the lack of necessary infrastructure like 4G/5G or broadband in certain areas. Economic barriers contribute to the exclusion of people from poorer countries and demographics, making this a critical area of focus.
2. **Disability and Inclusion:** Widely mentioned issues include challenges for people with disabilities such as visual impairments, motion sickness, and other physical disabilities. The design of XR hardware and software plays a significant role in either including or excluding users with disabilities.
3. **Diversity in Representation:** Issues around the representation of females, indigenous people, and people of color in XR content and development roles are significant. The importance of customizable avatars in XR platforms supports diverse identities, reflecting the need for broad representation.
4. **Technical Issues and Accessibility:** Concerns about lag and latency, along with the need for hardware to be universally designed to accommodate various levels of vision, hearing, and motor skills, are crucial technical barriers that need addressing.
5. **Language and Age Barriers:** Language skills and age are noted as barriers, particularly impacting those who do not speak major languages and older individuals who may lack digital literacy.
6. **Inclusivity in Content and Professional Use Cases:** The development of XR applications should consider diverse user groups, including professional use cases, to ensure content inclusivity.
7. **Cultural and Social Considerations:** Issues like targeted harassment based on avatar appearance and the need for culturally sensitive content highlight the importance of being mindful of social dynamics and cultural diversity in XR platforms.

3.3. Insights transformed into requirements from a theoretical perspective

In D7.1., two methods for addressing ethics in XR were proposed: ethical Technology Assessment (eTA) and Technology Acceptance Model (TAM). Technology Assessment (TA) aims to anticipate unintended negative consequences from emerging technological advancements, thereby facilitating well-informed policymaking concerning the new technology. eTA is a framework which aims to find and characterise the ethical aspects of an emerging technology (Palm & Hansson, 2006). In D7.1, six key criteria were identified and proposed for the eTA of XR technology. The six dimensions of the key criteria are:

1. **Informed consent** (concerns with upholding respect for individual autonomy, promoting transparency)
2. **Privacy & Security** (concerns with protecting the user data and the users)
3. **Accessibility** (concerns with accessible to all users regardless of their physical, cognitive, and sensory abilities)
4. **Content standards** (concerns about the appropriateness of the content)
5. **Fairness** (concerns about being fair to all population and not discriminate any groups or minorities)
6. **Social responsibility** (concerns minimizing the negative consequences to the society)

The survey's ethical categories and questions covered all these dimensions and complements these six criteria very well. Table 3. presents the relationship between the dimensions and the questions from the survey.

eTA ethics criteria	Survey categories	Questions with mean scores
Informed consent	Data & Tech Use	Q10 (4.35) explicit consent
Privacy & Security	Data & Tech Use	Q8 (4.27), Q9 (4.22) address privacy from an individual perspective, Q19 (2.06), Q21(1.61) address data use & security from organizational and industry level, Q24 (1.75) addresses data security from the regulatory level
Accessibility	Human Rights	Q14 (3.61) Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion (DEI)
Content Standards	Data & Tech Use	Q15 (3.09) addresses the avatar manipulation issues Q24 (1.75) addresses the awareness of ethical standards
Fairness	Human Rights	Q11(1.72) equal representation, Q12 (2.14) Exclusion, Q25 (2.72) autonomy & freedom
Social responsibility	Societal Economic & Environmental (SE&E)	Q32 (2.77) social inequality, Q34 (3.23) job disruption and Q36 (3.63) SE&E considerations

Table 3. Relationship between eTA criteria and survey questions

Figure 7: Responses categorised per ethics categories for eTA dimensions

For the informed consent criteria from the eTA, Question Q10, focusing on explicit consent, received the highest mean score of 4.35 from the participants, indicating its significance in upholding ethical standards in XR applications. For the Privacy & Security criteria, questions Q8, Q9, Q19, Q21, and Q24 collectively emphasize the importance of ensuring privacy and security from individual, organizational, industry, and regulatory perspectives. The mean scores for these questions indicate a high level of concern and importance for privacy at a personal level. The low mean score of Q24 indicates the general lack of awareness of standards for maintaining integrity and ethical practices for data and technology use in XR. For the Content standards criteria, particularly addressing issues such as avatar manipulation are important as Q15 received a mean score of 3.09. Social Responsibility criterion encompasses considerations related to societal, economic, and environmental impacts. Questions Q32, Q34, and Q36 addressed issues such as social inequality, job disruption, and broader societal and environmental considerations. These questions received moderate to high mean scores, indicating their importance in promoting social responsibility. While fairness is important, questions related to this criterion received relatively lower mean scores compared to others. However, this might be due to the high number of 'do not know' responses to the question meaning a general lack of awareness around this topic. Figure 7. shows the survey responses with their ethics categories and mean scores plotted against the eTA ethics criteria.

The Technology Acceptance Model (Venkatesh et al, 2008) proposes seventeen dimensions:

1. **Subjective norms** (social influence towards using XR technology)
2. **Experience** (own's experience with XR technology)
3. **Voluntariness** (own's free will to use XR technology)
4. **Image** (perception that using XR technology will enhance own status within a given social system)
5. **Job relevance** (belief that XR technology is applicable for performing the job or activity)
6. **Output quality** (belief that the using XR technology performs well for the task or activity at hand)
7. **Result demonstrability** (belief that the results of using XR technology are explicit, tangible, and communicable)
8. **Self-efficacy** (belief in own ability to perform a task or activity while using XR technology)
9. **Perceptions of external control** (perception of community resources and support for facilitating the usage of XR technology)

10. **Anxiety** (degree of apprehension or fear when faced with using XR technology)
11. **Playfulness** (the degree of cognitive spontaneity when using XR technology)
12. **Perceived enjoyment (the extent to which using XR technology is perceived enjoyable per se, independently of performance)**
13. **Objective usability** (actual level of effort for completing tasks or activities with XR technology)
14. **Perceived usefulness**
15. **Perceived ease of use**
16. **Intention to use**
17. **Usage behavior**

The appropriate dimensions of TAM3 were mapped with survey responses to relevant questions in table 4 and figure 8. Since user experience (UX) related dimensions of TAM 3 such as usability, usefulness, and ease of use are addressed in WP6, the current mapping will be consolidated in the next task (T7.4) with findings from WP6 in terms of use cases, best practices, and user experience.

XR ethics concerns related to data and technology use, human rights, societal, economic, and environmental aspects are expected to affect the XR technology acceptance. Table 4. provides a mapping of survey questions and relevant TAM3 dimensions.

TAM3 dimensions	Survey categories & Questions
Subjective norms	SE&E Q36 consider SE&E; Human Rights Q14 diversity equity inclusion; SE&E Q32 social inequality; Human Rights Q25 autonomy & freedom impacts;
Experience	
Voluntariness	
Image	
Job relevance	SE&E Q34 disrupt traditional jobs;
Output quality	
Result demonstrability	
Self-efficacy	Data & Tech use Q17 generative AI impacts;
Perceptions of external control	Data & Tech use Q10 explicit consent; Human Rights Q27 infringement of privacy & freedom of expression
Anxiety	Data & Tech use Q9 privacy professionally; Data & Tech use Q10 explicit consent; Data & Tech use Q9 privacy professionally; Data & Tech use Q24 confident that regulations protect user data; Data & Tech use Q15 avatars manipulation & misrepresentation;
Playfulness	
Perceived enjoyment	
Objective usability	
Perceived usefulness	
Perceived ease of use	
Intention to use	
Usage behavior	

Table 4. Relationship between TAM dimensions and survey questions

Figure 8: Responses categorised per ethics categories for TAM3 dimensions

4 Knowledge Tool

For sharing the identified stakeholders’ needs and requirements, we investigated several online knowledge management platforms and tools such as Confluence, Zoho Wiki, Dokuwiki, etc. These online knowledge management tools enable to share the elicited body of requirements from T7.2 in the form of a concept map (Appendix 4) or Wiki on the XR4Human website. However, to align with other ongoing efforts for knowledge representation in the project, it was decided to use the proposed knowledge representation tool from WP4, and this will be described below.

4.1 Mapping of knowledge in the online tool

Currently, a knowledge representation tool is being developed in WP4 for the WP4.2 deliverable. This tool also aims to capture insights from deliverables across different WPs, for online presentation on the XR4Human website. We tried to align our present work utilizing the same knowledge representation tool using the concept of a tram-map with lines and stations. In WP4.2, the lines correspond to the stakeholders’ categories, and the stations to clusters of standards that are intended to a given category of stakeholders. In Task 7.2, all stakeholders went through all the survey questions. Therefore, it was decided to use only one tram-line, allowing all to go through all stations, with stations corresponding to the various survey topics and color of the line corresponding to the stakeholder categories. Due to these differences, it was decided to develop a high-fidelity mock-up specifying the requirements from the knowledge representation tool for T7.2 before online implementation.

In the following, a high-fidelity mock-up illustrating all features specified is described (figures 7, 8, 9). Then, the initial partial implementation into a prototype tool from WP4 is provided in figure 10.

For the knowledge representation tool for WP7, a variety of design options were considered, such as more advanced visualizations (e.g., clusters of topics based on ethics categories) and interactions with either the lines (e.g., clicking on a stakeholder line would show the effective of the specific stakeholder category) or the stations (e.g., rings representing the stakeholder feedback to the given topic with its

priority rating, as well as a pop-up window providing detailed information about the particular topic and possibly links to external resources related to the corresponding topic). Figure 9. illustrates the main visualization layer of the tool.

Figure 9: High-fidelity mock-up of the online knowledge representation tool for XR ethical requirements

The demographics data from the survey is visualised at the top row with the help of donut charts. Donut chart is a type of ring with more layers of information. With these special rings, when the mouse cursor is hovered over the chart additional information could be visualised. Figure 10. shows an example interaction for the demographic data from the tool.

Figure 10: Interaction layer of the visualisation of demographic data from survey

Following the demographic data, the topics from the survey are clustered based on the thematic ethics categories. The results of each ethics topic are visualised in coloured rings with mean rating displayed in the middle of the ring. The colours of the rings are dynamic based on the ranked priority (Green for high, Orange for moderate, and yellow for low). The grey line that goes through all the rings depicts the results for all stakeholder categories. It is also possible to filter the results for a specific stakeholder category by selecting it from the list displayed in the left. Then the colour of the line, mean value & colour of the ring change according to the results specific to the selected stakeholder category. In addition, when a specific ring is clicked a pop-up window with additional information related to the corresponding ethics

topic will appear. The pop-up window contains requirements, examples, and priorities from the sample stakeholders (Figure 11).

Figure 11: Pop-up layer for detailed information of requirements for specific topic

The specifications for the XR ethics online knowledge representation tool are currently being applied and tested in the tool being developed in WP4. Figure 12. illustrates the first prototype implementation of the knowledge representation from the survey using this tool (N=69).

Figure 12: Results from the survey captured in the initial knowledge representation tool prototype from WP4

5 Conclusion & Perspectives

During the allocated period for D7.2., 112 valid responses were received to the survey's 19 rating questions, as well as the equivalent of 26 pages of responses to the 11 open feedback questions, with a response rate varying from 37% to 12% depending on the respondents' engagement with the question.

The survey aimed to capture stakeholders' ethical needs and requirements in XR through ethics perspectives such as data and technology use, human rights, and societal, economic, and environmental concerns.

Quantitatively, the results highlight several key concerns ranked by the mean score given by participants. Issues surrounding explicit consent, privacy, and the need for ethical guidelines ranked high, indicating a strong awareness and concern for these areas among participants. Meanwhile, aspects such as equal representation, security concerns, and human rights issues scored lower, indicating either less concern or perhaps less familiarity with these topics.

The qualitative data through participant examples adds depth to these findings, providing valuable insights into specific experiences and considerations of stakeholders.

Combined together, the survey results provide a rich knowledge base focused specifically on ethics, as well as interesting insights in terms of user requirements that complement other existing efforts on general requirements for XR (e.g., EU Citizens' Panel on Virtual Worlds).

In addition, from a theoretical perspective, the survey's findings were mapped against the criteria proposed by eTA and TAM3, indicating a broader alignment with key ethical considerations in XR technologies. These identified models adapted to XR specific ethical considerations could contribute to a systematic framework for ethical development and deployment of XR technologies in the future.

The identified ethical requirements for the stakeholders elicited by the survey have been implemented in a knowledge representation tool aiming to make it available on the XR4Human website as part of a central repository for the collected data, analyses, and discussions on XR ethics related topics.

When it comes to the key contribution of the survey to ongoing XR ethics research efforts, we may emphasize the specific question on the impacts of generative AI on XR ethics, as well as questions related to XR avatar manipulation, XR possibly creating social inequalities, XR possible job disruptions, need for XR ethics guidelines, as well as the need to increase XR ethics awareness.

Overall, the results from this task provide a multifaceted view of the current ethical landscape in XR. They suggest a heightened awareness and concern for issues of consent, privacy, and ethical guidelines. At the same time, it reveals potential areas where awareness may need to be raised, such as regulations to protect user data and the broader societal implications of XR technology. These various detailed categories of stakeholder ethics requirements gathered in this task will be consolidated with other relevant WPs from the project for providing a solid ethics foundation that will serve for the rating system for empowering XR users in Task 7.4.

The survey is still active, and we aim to reach around 150 respondents during summer 2024, as recommended by the EU citizen panels.

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7 Appendix 1: Raw open feedback

Q 13 Please provide examples related to equal representation or exclusion in XR

Still very low numbers of female, indigenous and people of color represented not only within in-XR experiences, but also at the other side of the fence with developers, design, marketing and production. (Organizations like Women in Immersive Tech can help promote better equality)

Exclusion in XR may be related to not having access to the content and/or the devices for economical reasons.

Most platforms have pretty customizable avatars to support this issue

On social VR platforms, I have seen events that are mainly white or black with very little mixing. But you also see this in the physical world. I do see separation based on political views as well.

Targeted ads?

These technologies circumvent the typical physiological expressions of race/gender that predispose people to bias and allow humans to connect to other humans in the circumstances and appearances they choose. XV platforms are one of the most equalizing platforms there are on these terms by their nature.

Gender inequality is a major one, especially within VC and other funding for projects

The representation within development groups is a factor and those that have access to the technology and be able to raise their voices

Technology latecomers, people and organizations resisting change, any area where internet access is not available for technical or economic reasons would be underrepresented, if not totally excluded.

disabilities, wearing glasses, motion sickness, people lacking digital literacy

The straps of many XR headsets are still "incompatible" with hairstyles and head wear that many women or ethnic minorities often have (braids, Afros, turbans, etc.)

Eyesight

People with visual disabilities

Training systems in particular may not always need to include all groups or demographics of the human population. For example, flight simulators require visual perception and coordination skills so requiring that such system can be operated by users with reduced or no vision (that would never be permitted to fly a real aircraft) would be inappropriate. Age and ability (physical/mental) as criteria for exclusion can therefore be appropriate in some cases for specialized applications.

The chosen hardware and software solution may exclude if it is not designed universally with specific groups in mind.

An anticipated cost of buy in for tech, software, etc. could and probably would marginalize and exclude many poor countries and demographics. As there is also a language barrier in terms of English and other major spoken languages, people who do not meet the required language skills would be excluded. There is also the threshold connected to age and tech competence, which would render many older people (maybe

60+) unable to operate and make use of XR tech. And lastly, people with disabilities such as sight, hearing, or movement would probably face some issues in various degrees.

Any solution should take into account wide population groups

seen some demos in IFE

Given that in most XR applications you can be anywhere between a cat and a 6-legged dragon, I would say most applications by themselves are inclusive. That is not to say the users themselves are.

XR industry has several equal representation groups that bring together developers and users on volunteer-basis. XR is something people feel passionate about, and it is all about the technology and solutions rather than historical burdens.

Visual representation of abilities, cultures and. Design of gear to facilitate use of those who wear glasses.

"Socioeconomic and geographic reasons are likely going to be the biggest hinderance at the current time. The devices, solutions and 4G/5G connectivity are too expensive to many users. As long as you have the money, I don't expect that having a certain skin color or belonging to a religious minority or have different gender identity is going to be a significant source of exclusion in XR. If that is stated as a fact I would be interested in seeing empirical evidence of how significant it actually is. Some geographic regions might not have 4G/5G connectivity or broadband broadly available causing real exclusion based on where you live in the world. Limited access to money is in my opinion the most pervasive source of severe preventable forms of exclusion in the modern world.

Also, as the more highly immersive solutions and devices are not yet main stream, except from smartphone based AR and thus people with diverse levels of ability might not be well served and thus excluded by failure to take universal design into proper account. That could be variations in vision, hearing, motor skills, mental abilities etc. so after socioeconomic and geographic sources of exclusion I expect this to be a real cause of exclusion."

Between people familiar vs non familiar with new technologies (numeric fraction)

In VR environments mostly white people are portrayed.

Young, poor

Exclusion: disabilities (eyesight, moving) obscure a number of users

Exclusion: lack of options in creation of avatars, including selection of clothes

Inclusion: breaks language barriers, as visual content can deliver the information with limited text

Generative AI is used to produce visual content that may exclude some genders and races.

Some people are extremely sensitive to lag and/or latency and cannot work with current hardware. For all other

As a general user of the technology, I'm curious about how people with vision disabilities will use XR? Are they excluded from the user group altogether? I haven't used any of the recent XR devices, but I use AR on mobile quite often.

Developing professional use cases in XR you would expect that XR application would be used by and for particular groups of people."

Some people are extremely sensitive to lag and/or latency and cannot work with current hardware. For all other

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Developing professional use cases in XR you would expect that XR application would be used by and for particular groups of people.

general communal job pools (LinkedIn, Glassdoor, indeed) are not explicitly working on being more inclusive, indie creators are without funding support, so ideas fail / do not progress

I don't know how to interpret "Could exclude". If this means "to what extent is it acceptable to exclude", I profess that any production solution beyond PoC/Pilot phase should never exclude various cultures, ethnicities, or demographics.

For exclusion, it is more about people who have disabilities that make it difficult for them to experience XR (for example, reduced vision, motion sickness, or related).

Targeted harassment based on avatar appearance excludes vulnerable groups.

The formulation of Question 12 is not very clear. Hard to understand what exactly you want to find out.

Since XR is still in its fledgling state, there is a high probability of limited representation of audience.

In most XR platforms there is a choice of Avatars with diverse identity and an option to costuming, which gives you the possibility to adjust to your own needs.

Expensive for most public

The content is still not very rich for XR, but in my experience inclusivity has been a big issue and there is representation (sometimes in strange ways, like is there really a need for full Muslim coverage/niqab in one of the platforms?). I guess it depends on who the audience and the clients are.

XR models may not be able to adapt to the needs of specific user groups and thus exclude them

I have not seen many common applications of XR yet."

Q 16 Please provide examples related to manipulation and misrepresentation using avatars in XR

A man posing as a female and interacting with wrong or harmful intent.

Also, a man posing as a man and sexually harassing or verbally bullying.

Risk of child abuse through using a "child-like" avatar to make contact with children.

People can modify avatars to their own desire. More flexible than photo profiles.

I think most people try to represent themselves as they are, but it is very possible, and I have seen people choose different races than they are. I try when I can to pick a skin tone that does not exist. Like purple. I did for a 1 day, choose a black skin tone to see what people's reactions would be. Some black people were offended and while people tended to ignore me.

There is no clear relationship between an avatar and the person represented by the avatar.

Older person disguising as younger person to groom people (typically done with voice changer and stuff). This is something that is an issue in social platforms like VRChat, so I assume the same can be done for XR. I have also personally been targeted for scamming by a pair of people that pretended to have issues that

could be solved by money, highly dangerous as this can be done over time to build trust as well. (I did not fall for this obviously, but I am sure others have and will)

Given that all avatars are adopted by their users, there's no basis on which to assume anything about an avatar means anything about the user using it. People may choose an avatar for many reasons that may or may not even be related to how they wish to be perceived. As long as users are aware of this, avatar choices can hopefully be reduced to aesthetic or functional concerns and be devoid of the baggage of persona and image in everyday life.

Concerned about sexual assault and other misogynistic crime in metaverse spaces featuring avatars.

No example, just a reasoning. Any chatbot making use of preferred dialogue techniques will, whether they make clear it is artificial or not, provide an instinctive feel of recognition. The double message here creates an unclarity which leads to an intellectual understanding of the virtuality, while a subliminal feel of reality prevails.

lobbying to a specific view, or product

Manipulation and misrepresentation is actually what many people look for in experiences like VRChat (presenting themselves with non-human avatars).

Not being able to select desired gender/color

Practically every computer game that uses as avatar represents the user in a way that does not match their real-life gender or appearance, so it depends on the application. Most computer games also hide the real identify of the user from other users. However, that is part of the role play of the game. More worrying would be in "real world" systems where identity theft is perpetrated using an avatar to support tricking other users.

As seen with AI generated images, videos, audio, even if the public is made aware that what they are seeing and hearing is fake, there is still a lasting impacting from seeing/hearing said image or audio. I believe some of the same issues could be problematic in XR, without being able of concrete examples.

Avatars are 100% digital and have no real-world context to them. You can augment the appearance and the voice of an avatar to any preference, and you can assign any tasks to the avatar you want regardless of your own ability to execute them. I don't believe the human brain is capable of distinguishing a difference if a message is coming from an avatar or a real human being, it will consume the information as it is.

People could use avatars that don't represent them or their organization to get information and money. With no ethics room for identity theft. Its why data protection is so important.

I have limited experience of that as I spend time in virtual worlds very sporadically typically many months apart. But in systems where I have been given the opportunity to build personal avatars by adjusting appearances such as skin color, hairstyles clothing and body shapes there is at least a decent level of opportunity to get pretty close to highly diverse individual appearances. There might be some limits on the extreme ends, for instance if you try to build a very obese or very anorexic avatar. So, a very thin or very obese person might not find a way to recreate close resemblance of their appearance and might experience that their particular body shape is not accepted on a particular platform.

The same way as disinformation is constructed (using e.g. AI), but now manifested in avatars/people that are not real.

Adults pretending to connect with children.

Social Engineering & phishing: Posing as someone else (familiar or famous person) to get personal information from strangers, posing as younger/ older to sexually exploit others

Bots & AI: potential flood of machine generated entities, increasing distrust in virtual environments.

FAKE NEWS ELECTORAL (known example Obama)

Realistic avatars not showcasing enough racial and gender diversity in realistic digital worlds; Not enough personalization features; inability to upload owned avatar.

Never thought about that. Do not think that using avatars provides any value in professional use cases."

Realistic avatars not showcasing enough racial and gender diversity in realistic digital worlds; Not enough personalization features; inability to upload owned avatar.

Never thought about that. Do not think that using avatars provides any value in professional use cases.

cultural appropriation, grooming, lack of controls for age-appropriate content

Avatars can represent trusted people and be used to manipulate others through persuasion, misdirection, and misrepresentation while presenting itself as a trusted person or a member of a trusted group or organization. Trusted people could be either explicit persons, or could be trusted by association, such as simply by looking and acting as a professional, or by appearing to belong to a trusted organization or group. This is deeply concerning.

Not sure what you mean by question 15... perhaps it's the phrasing. Are you talking about misrepresentation from a legal sense (as in, deep fakes or identity theft), or the philosophical sense (as in, is an avatar actually an authentic representation of the self). How does that relate to "XR solutions"... don't know what you mean there.

False representation of individuals, groups, and or cultures

Social engineering attacks

Deceptive marketing

Psychological Manipulation

I have conducted research on how avatars or roles given to users in VR films/games are applied in manipulative ways in XR storytelling on history. These are used in radical right memory politics and disinformation campaigns. XR storytelling is a perfect propaganda tool because of how it impacts users' autobiographical memory and transforms biased stories into users' personal XR experiences. This has been/is done in Poland, Russia, Saudi Arabia, etc.

For example, a person can illustrate the avatars relative to a celebrity and can easily perform an act of deception and gather falsely credibility.

This is an area that is developing, but due to the rising degree of realism and Ai technology avatars could be used for manipulation, fake news and propaganda.

40-year-old men pretending to be 20-year-old female

avatars can be shaped to provide cover to users with malicious intentions but also influence and lure the user into possibly dangerous situations

When using drag and drop options or commercial apps with integrated avatars the options to adapt them are very limited. You cannot for example change the age or physical aspects of an avatar. Think Ready Player Me or any for that matter that are not specifically developed for avatar design.

As a student and undergraduate researcher, my experience with avatars was with Microsoft Rocket Box and Ready Player Me; I acknowledge there are more readily available avatar creation tools. Nonetheless, rocket box had some diversity in appearances with careers and skin tones, but no gender-neutral avatars and by default had some seemingly racial stereotypes in the skin tones of people in specific professions they portrayed. Ready Player Me provided, in contrast, an ability to select appearances that were not humanistic, which in my opinion allows users the opportunity to abstract parts of their identity that they do or don't feel comfortable displaying. Furthermore, if I remember correctly, a variety of body types as well as physical abilities were not represented in the rocket box kit. While it's possible for users to manipulate limbs of rocket box avatars to reflect someone sitting in a wheelchair, it would be difficult to match the art style. Furthermore, it would not be possible to use either tool kit to represent artificial limbs, as I recall at least for the state of the tools at the time of use (around 2021-2022)."

Q 18 Please provide examples related to ethical impacts of Generative AI in XR

Deep fakes Imposter, real humans, false identity, manipulation, copyright infringement

Biased chatbots.

AI will be used for data and audience manipulation and in XR it'll be more effective

If AI is used to steal the look, feel, or art of a world builder or if AI is used to pose as a person but is not real. They could give advice that is harmful or unethical.

Shares many of the ethics issues of generative AI in the real world probably.

If not moderated carefully, narratives by Generative AI in XR can transport stereotypes and misinformation.

I hardly see anything which is not already questionable on an ethics standpoint: the nature of Generative AI carries some biases, which are not avoidable but could be mitigated. I am especially thinking about race and sex.

automated generation of content based on interests

Generative AI can be biased due to datasets that come from scraping the internet are unlikely to be accurate/balanced/true

Generative AI can result in ethically questionable results based on the input data used to train it and lack of rules to validate and filter results. There was a recent case where the AI was overcompensating for gender and ethnicity balance, and generating images that were supposed to represent historical events with ethnically inappropriate results.

Content of Generative AI may generate inappropriate situations if not controlled properly

Ties into my previous answer. Generative AI and XR could be "weaponized" in terms of changing public opinion and disinformation campaigns.

Can there be a risk of bias in programming?

It is easy to script an avatar to give speeches that look like they are coming from a person but are fully computer generated and possibly the opposite of what the actual human might say. Generative AI in XR can produce content much faster than a human who needs to use their brain to form a sentence and produce intellectual outputs.

Identity theft, catfishing, fraud, and money theft.

One aspect is how frontier labs as of this data continue to train their models on the creative work of individuals who have not been asked for permission or have any plausible way to be compensated for their

creative work. Another one is how easy it still is to "jailbreak" the generative models to produce output with harmful or illegal content.

AI is biased per definition. Training data is biased, and this bias is amplified by wide AI application/ trust in AI.

Bots & AI: potential flood of machine generated entities, increasing distrust in virtual environments.

Ask Midjourney to produce an image representing African Art for example.

The AI was educated on the big data of white and Western culture.

Fake info

As a technology, gen AI enables many ethical issues related to truth and trust, conscience of the other, relationships and shared social concepts in many different vertical areas.

Have not thought of any."

As a technology, gen AI enables many ethical issues related to truth and trust, conscience of the other, relationships and shared social concepts in many different vertical areas.

Have not thought of any.

neural marketing / neural rights breaches, invasive messaging

To the extent that AI makes it possible to mimic real life and real people more faithfully than ever before while also being able to individualize this fake reality based on known data about each individual recipient opens the door to significant psychological manipulation. This is deeply concerning as well.

Again, "In XR solutions" makes for an ambiguous question. Do you mean, to what extend do I think Generative AI impacts ethics? A lot.

Generative AI may hallucinate or create compelling arguments for things that may be ethically dubious.

Possibility of manipulation using AI-powered artificial avatars"

Privacy, Identity issues, bias and discrimination, misinformation, authenticity of information, psychological impact, intellectual property, cultural misrepresentation based on training data used, accessibility.

Again, in relation to memory politics and propaganda, gen AI can be employed to steer users' perception of reality/past/politics in deliberately biased and manipulative ways, and without users being aware of how they are manipulated.

Generative AI needs to achieve more maturity before it is pressed on to the XR space. If not there a high chance of mis representation of data and responses!

Synthetic voice, animation, or body representation of real people. AI personality models (digital human twins) that could be used to predict behavior or manipulate the user.

Depends on the developer, how they use generative AI. Recently, one great voice actor died, and in order to honor him, the community started discussing using generative AI to keep on using his voice for the character in the game.

It could use data from other users that could be private.

esp. given that the regulations are not well developed yet. ethics includes issues such as using artist's work without consent and presenting generative work as human. but on the other hand, AI allows for so much creativity, so there should be a balance.

XR content can be used remotely to train models without the user approval

All models are trained on datasets that are susceptible to containing biases, whether obvious or subconscious. For example, creating an AI-based nurse capable of predicting diagnoses to provide suggestions to doctors would need to be trained on a massive dataset of medical diagnoses. Without careful consideration of the data sources when creating a training dataset, given that it is documented that race and gender have historically influenced medical diagnoses in scenarios where that information is irrelevant, it would be likely that the generative model used in the XR diagnosis tool would include unintentional biases in its diagnoses depending on the information it is trained on."

Q 20 Please provide examples related to security in XR

On the ddw platform, in the Veemgebouw building 8th floor. Don't remember the name sorry.

And a group virtual environment, I once saw a male avatar virtually harass another female avatar

I haven't really experienced security concerns yet. But I'm sure there are some we haven't thought of yet.

Tracking of biometric data in the HMD happens, but it is not clear what the platform/ manufacturers do with this.

Like all game modding communities, the security practices of VR game modders are not ideal and platform developers should (for many reasons) invest in robust and secure modding APIs which limit access/risk to user information while simultaneously allowing users a participatory and creative role in their own experience beyond just running the software.

Casinos in VR are a good example.

Storage of data on the device

Every time I use the Meta headsets, I know for sure that the company-previously-known-as-Facebook is selling personal data to third parties that want to use it against my interests. Even if it is just for advertising.

Especially AR that requires sending pictures of the environment to a server can cause problems unless the destination is entirely understood and under control.

Cloud-based systems that send data to countries that they are not supposed to (e.g., sharing data from Europe with China or Russia without consent).

Currently any software developed solution that might impact on nuclear safety may have security issues to overcome.

You can create a digital version of the physical world in XR and if you have physical security access controls in the actual world, you might have gaps in the digital world. Also, the high-end XR headsets make the XR experience feel very realistic, hence what you experience in the digital world will generate physical, emotional, and mental experiences for the person using the devices.

Pokemon GO famously caused many users to be distracted from real world potential risks in the physical world context with lethal consequences. I see the use of Video Passthrough such as Apple Vision Pro outdoors as a physical high-risk situation as it might take replace your entire field of vision and field of sound by virtual content putting users in harms' way if used in a location that poses risk. That could be near traffic, near cliffs or steep and long stairs, in uneven terrain where loss of awareness might cause you to

stumble, near thorny vegetation or even near places one should not trespass as they are normally protected by armed security personnel authorized to shoot trespassers. I don't know of any systems that have this real-world awareness where the system will ensure that the user is not distracted by virtual content when that would be a security risk. The mitigation typically used is either self-erected virtual barriers like for instance the Meta, or the fading out of content in the Apple Vision Pro if a user starts running, which would normally be a high-risk activity with a video pass through.

Dedicated XR devices may have limited data security mechanisms, increased number of sensors and tracking (e.g. environment, hand motions, pupils) increases available sensitive information.

Can obstruct line of sight, can be more persuasive in phishing scenarios.

Pretty much all of them, as we're all just now having our first major security breaches in XR.

There are plenty of use cases in Healthcare and Defense where security is critically important.

Digital twin full body scan biometric data collection and the image rights going to the tech company, not the human original.

Few XR solutions offer true end-to-end security. Collaborative scenarios mandate large amounts of data to be transmitted between participants. This data is rarely encrypted in today's solutions.

What do you mean by XR solutions raising security concerns? Once again, the phrasing is extremely abstract and non-specific. Are you asking if technical "solutions" to XR problems have themselves raised security concerns? Then, sure.

Haven't been in an XR environment that raised a security concern, but I can imagine that one could create such situations.

Possible misuse of digital twins for terrorist attack planning.

Prone to issues during the adaptation phase

Personal data like Voice, facial expressions, animations, actions of the user in a controlled environment are streamed and processed, which can lead to security and privacy concerns.

in my case, security was too high, so I wasn't able to use a colleague's headset for work, and adding additional accounts was forbidden by an unclear error.

video or sound in critical infrastructure analyzed remotely"

Q22 Please provide examples related to ethical issues in XR

Going into the experience blind, not knowing what you are consenting to.

We have not personally experienced this, but we are aware of customers being concerned of data and privacy issues via biometrics and tracking through facial recognition via augmented reality, and also virtual reality and head mounted displays.

I have not had experience with unethical data use, but I'm pretty sure it's happening.

If Holocaust survivors are represented via volumetric video in VR, we need to be careful how to represent and manipulate the volumetric asset in order to respect the witness.

I'm answering as a private person. We don't use this at work. Ref q21

At this point, it is an issue we are professionally interested in

The XR devices are full of sensors to capture the surrounding environment. While this is necessary for spatial navigation mechanisms, it can also be used to spy on the users.

Use of anthropometrical data may exclude individuals.

Our industry is based in an area of the country where ethics diversity is relatively low.

Conflicts of interest (public vs. private research), and safety issues for users

One example is how the business model of Pokemon Go leverages the game mechanics that users get excited about to nudge and manipulate them to go to distinct places that the custom pays Niantic to direct their users to, without specifically informing their customers that they are being manipulated in this way. This is a sneaky erosion of people's autonomous agency for the purpose of fulfilling the commercial customers' needs rather than catering to the actual XR end user needs. People might be led towards places they should not be or places where they would be vulnerable to commercial exploitation by Niantic's paying customers. It is one step further than the typical surveillance capitalist business model that captures the users' mental attention keeping them on the platform for longer so more can be learned about their personalities and desires so as to be presented with the ads most likely to cause "conversion" in line with the advertisers' interest. With the location-based manipulation you can capture both attention and the physical presence of the end users to create more powerful conversion and manipulation.

We experiment with a VR environment through a moral lab. Accessibility of certain groups is an issue. Another issue is the question who decides on what to show during an ethic experiment (moral authority).

Have not thought of any.

In my current company, we are highly focused on ethics, Diversity and Inclusion and governance, but are pre-release so not yet measurable. At previous companies, the lack of concern or even awareness around ethics and governance has been concerning.

The ethical issues match most with personal information issues that relate to GDPR or general research ethics.

Targeting based on biometric data and inference of sensitive characteristics/medical conditions."

Meta together with the Polish government mainstreaming VR in school history education in Poland. Use of data does not enter the public discussion at all.

Inadequate avatar to represent specific user demographics for certain tasks. Thus, making it difficult to analyze complex tasks given the potential demographic that may perform them.

N/A

AI driven daring avatars.

We do not use XR at our organization.

Q26 Please provide examples related to autonomy and personal freedom in XR

Personal data used for tracking and algorithms and advertisements and unwanted marketing campaigns.

It's not autonomy or personal freedom I'm worried about. It's the manipulation of opinion that I'm worried about. Making someone believe something that is not true to shape their opinion about something that could cause an action like shooting people in a church of a different religion.

Leaving key features behind paywalls, especially on so

Outside of enthusiast and gaming, there are extremely concerning applications of brain scanning data being explored by employers which raise foundational privacy concerns for the entirety of that new technology space. For references, check out *The Battle for Your Brain* written by Nita A. Farahany.

I think XR solutions such as training and mental health support can hugely positively impact autonomy and personal freedom but are currently not being deployed to the right extent or in the right ways.

No example, just a reasoning. Generative AI relates to impact in the same way all technology will: it will enable more complex work to be done, but simultaneously it also enables people to postpone or avoid making decisions. People's agency is a combination of what they can take decisions on, and what they actually decide. Taking away the necessity to decide, will therefore automatically take away people's agency. If freedom of choice and self-management is seen as important elements in people's self-actualization, the application of AI, is linked to ethical issues.

Biased views, 100%-time monitoring/influence.

For some people, maybe those who struggle with social situations, this could allow them to be social in a totally new and more realistic manner, and even help them be better in real life situations. This would probably apply to many different people with different struggles. On the other hand, there would probably be exclusion here as well. And thinking of professional use, this may represent an exciting way of working, but for others a technology that scares them, or seems highly inaccessible. All this meaning that some may feel more freedom, and others more boxed in, and a loss of previous freedom and ability to do their job the way they know.

Autonomy is limited by the rules of the artificial construct. The limits of personal freedom are more or less constrained than the real world. These differences may be manipulated by commercial interests to exploit humans.

XR doesn't have to follow the laws of physics or be limited to actual world capabilities. I hope and believe that XR will enable people with different capabilities to have experiences that would not be possible for them if they didn't have XR. For example, a person who cannot leave their home due to physical restrictions can use XR to travel.

Monitoring of location and behavior opens people to marketing and other control.

If there is bias in the options provided to users, even in the name of "personalization," then personal freedoms become limited.

For a specific example I gave a description of the Pokemon go business model that erodes its uses autonomy. To take a bigger framing - in general, both the game mechanism of classical computer games and the social media psychological reward mechanism are highly capable of capturing attention. Such mechanism could be greatly enhanced and intensified in immersive experiences making it potentially much harder for a user that is "captured" by the mechanism to use their agency consciously to break out of the experience. This should make regulators vigilant and pay attention to the level and intensity of end user capture in immersive solutions and therefore highly skeptical of business models that profit from increased levels of capturing the user's attention and manipulating the users' behaviors.

It will ultimately change important things, such as perception of what is real (Epistemic Security), and influence e.g., how we perceive politics, communication, our role as consumer, sexual development.

Influence by Fake News on social categories with no or low education on technology and media.

Higher potential of profiling

Continuous data capture and its processing by private AI's can fundamentally tilt sales and marketing processes towards the AI owners' side and irrevocably impact the agency and free will of consumers and citizens.

Have not thought of any.

Given that Meta's devices are some of the current best in the industry, Meta's historical lack of discipline and concern about ethics and governance, lack of meaningful systems level and application level XR opt-in options, the unprecedented ability to collect new types of data, such as facial expressions and eye movement, and given that their business model relies heavily on leveraging personal data, I fear that personal data is already being misused and will continue to be for the foreseeable future by both Meta and other XR application developers.

What are you asking here? XR solutions are what, exactly?

Nudging based on biometric data misuse

Manipulating users' perception of self, others, politics, working on users' emotions without them being aware that this is done.

XR in some cases can create a sense of dependency and since lot of the mental models are still in training phase it would be a while before we are able to attend a totality

There is the danger of AI generated personality models which could be sold to third parties and which could have an impact on autonomy and personal freedom.

It could positively impact lives of people who have some sort of disability.

I mean they are not ubiquitous enough yet to be a problem. maybe in the future. but they are quite exclusive based on the mere basis of digital literacy and economic access to the tech.

XR can provide a channel for remote surveillance of user environment and actions which can be used by a variety of actors

If data collection in XR solutions has relatively minimal regulation, the data could be used to influence general public users' decisions on what apps to work with. Terrifyingly, the thought of using biometric data collection (such as using eye tracking to interpret what users are visually observing on something like a webpage displayed in an XR headset) to create more targeted experiences, whether in advertisements or suggested content, could lead to influencing users in their choices and interests as well as their ability to foster more diverse personal interests and interact with a wider audience and range of human experiences."

Q28 Please provide examples related to privacy infringement and freedom of expression in XR

There could be a case of using somebody's data and privacy without their consent or permission, especially with regards to personal safety

XR is the best way for someone to show their freedom of expression. I don't think it takes it away. I think it is a powerful tool.

Censorship on social platforms, the typical ad data privacy infringement issues

Most of these platforms combine speech and association and tie them to an account around which social networks and communities are built. The accounts are increasingly subject to stronger self-identification requirements to create and as a result hold hostage those associations and that community which a user

builds around their account under the threat of isolation if the rules around expression change. Generally speaking (and true in XR as well), attempts to more closely police the freedom of expression come directly at the expense of privacy such that violations of any rules around expression can be actioned by officials more readily.

The way privacy and freedom of expression are approached in XR so far, is totally insufficient, because there is a lack of understanding of the underlying social processes. Freedom of expression, the right to not reveal your thoughts to all, are important, as is an understanding of collectivity and the limitations this brings on personal expression. Since collectivity comes in different scales and intensities, this shifting from total freedom to self-limitation is automatically a gradual process. While this is understood in the realms of the physical world, the digital world still treats the issue of privacy versus control as a dichotomy.

Filtering, banning, access denial to services or content based on limitation of the freedom of expression.

The never-ending discussion about whether to monitor the activity of the users to avoid them sharing contents that might not be allowed in certain countries (e.g., drawing neo-Nazi symbols might be legal in certain countries but not in Germany) is only getting worse in the XR space.

Gathering data the user may not be aware of and sending it to servers the user may not be aware of.

As there is no divide between me in the real world, and me in an extended reality setting, my actions are mine and mine only. I would not appreciate all my actions in a day to day scenario being recorded and stored for use, unless I was 100 percent sure it was fully anonymous. Even then I would be skeptical of what the data could be used for, and where they might end up. Is this another parameter my boss could use? How much value am I generating for an ad company like Google?

The aspect of freedom of expression is most under threat when there are very big, centralized platforms where there are few alternatives. That could be applications that have seen significant network effect that large portions of the user-population might be more or less compelled to use to be a part of the community or in a potential totalitarian government controlled system, as one might suspect a regime like China, Iran or North Korea might deploy in this space. The Facebooks, App-stores etc. of the world that sort of locks users into a situation where alternatives are either not possible (Apple app store) or not yet viable due to the network effect (Facebook when you are a parent who needs to coordinate with other parents where all children's activities tend to be organized via Facebook groups), or in the case of Frontier AI labs who create the most capable generative AI solutions. In all such highly centralized platforms where users lack real viable alternatives there is a risk that the ethical and political biases of a small elite group in a small geographic location sets the rules of the game for what forms and content of speech is allowed either within a totalitarian regime or for the case of the leading big-tech companies across all sorts of jurisdictions in all parts of the world, regardless of what people in different places feel is right or just. Things that can be spoken openly and freely about where they live are suddenly prohibited on the platform and vice versa. For XR we see this concentration in the Meta and Apple ecosystems, and this destroys the possibility of local jurisdictions across the world to define the rules according to their cultural and political milieu.

I don't believe that freedom of expression will be so impacted as freedom to decide will be.

Have not thought of any.

Avatar representation varies greatly from platform to platform - freedom of personal expression is not always served - lack of choice of body shape, binary gender representation, religious suppression.

Basically the same answer as for question 26

Are you referring to XR as a solution to... what, exactly? Why don't you just say "How concerned are you about the potential for XR to infringe on privacy..." If so, my concern is VERY HIGH.

Chilling effect of surveillance, speech being restricted based on jurisdiction, possible targeting of specific forms of expression by state actors."

N/A

This scenario is somewhat counter intuitive, but generative AI solutions are conditioned for ethical reasons, that is good and desirable, but it can also block out freedom of expression.

From a security point of view, I am afraid that both developers and end-users will be uncritical to using such systems. As long as the device has camera to provide XR, it might potentially record everything, which in the future might get leaked.

awareness of XR could lead into users restricting their expression and could violate privacy by providing access to user actions in different environments

See answer above regarding use of biometric data for targeted experiences."

Q30 Please provide examples related to human rights concerns in XR

Yes, but in a positive way, to raise awareness about things like human trafficking, domestic abuse, female genital mutilation, migration and more.

None

Kind of. I've seen XR being used to showcase when human rights have been taken from someone or a group of people. To showcase the evil in the world and build empathy towards it. These same tools could be used for the opposite result.

There are VR experiences where the user is put in a barrack of the concentration camp hearing the commands of a keeper. I think this violates the human rights of all the victims and the user as well.

Sexual assault cases, hate speech, bullying.

Without the ability to control (at hardware level) sensors like microphones and cameras, XR headsets can become the perfect tool of mass surveillance.

See explanation above. people in other jurisdictions can have their freedom of speech, or freedom from what they consider harmful speech infringed upon by terms defined by the political culture and biases prevalent amongst the elites living in the small geographies that create and own the big tech platforms.

Have not thought of any.

To the extent that American Disabilities Act (ADA) Accessible Designs compliance can be classified as a human right, few XR solutions meet even the most basic ADA requirements, particularly concerning blindness.

Not encountered any, but I think XR could be useful in exposing people to human rights issues.

My research focuses on how XR impacts human rights, so I have a whole thesis worth

Applications of VR in propaganda in Russia, including in a Russian history museum that has been created on the occupied territories of Ukraine. XR is used to suppress freedom of opinion and information.

N/A

I do not know."

Q33 Please provide examples related to social inequality in XR

It's a first world luxury. How many countries and cultures are we excluding?

In virtual reality, there is still a huge imbalance of experiences being created by males for a male audience.

In Augmented reality, experiences and environments are a lot more democratized to create communities with fairness and equality and inclusivity.

It'll actually help with this issue long term, not hurt.

The cost of XR will cause social inequality. Some people can participate while others cannot.

The applications are not accessible for everyone due to device costs, network availability and so on.

Again, in the future I am sure that not using XR solutions will leave you behind in society.

In VRChat I have observed inequality in the form of how "veteran" a user is, which is represented by a rank. There is also a distinction between people that have a paid subscription versus those that do not, and there have been many cases of bullying based on these factors."

I think, other than the hardware costs being somewhat of a barrier to entry, that these technologies are incredibly leveling in terms of giving people access and connectivity to anyone anywhere. Viewed as an extension of the Internet, these technologies enable a richer and less encumbered social landscape than reality in some cases. The potential for assistive technology in this space to give people virtual access, freedom, movement which they cannot physically experience is also exciting and acts to increase equality rather than reduce it.

Digital illiteracy already is a growing problem in large cities with poor population such as Rotterdam, leaving people behind. XR, while it may help just those who are illiterate because the immersive 3D experience may be easier to understand, may actually add to this problem, because it requires a high, and therefore expansive standard of equipment that exactly the target group of digital illiterates will not be able to afford.

Cost and access to the technology are factors.

No access to XR solutions due to a lack of resources, access or will to embrace change towards such technologies.

The price of (and skills necessary to use) XR devices is already deepening the Digital Divide.

XR solutions are generally only available for relatively expensive devices, and lower-end devices may not have the capabilities required for a good experience. Thus, more well-off people would be the ones that use it.

Some higher-end experiences may require very fast 5G connections, meaning they are only available to wealthy locations that can build such infrastructure."

Similar to mobile phones and computers in general, not all families or people can afford the latest technology and thus some become excluded.

Mentioned it previously. Buy in, tech competence, age, and many other aspects could create a divide between users and non-users. And as it is hard to say what XR will do, I am sure it will be highly beneficial for those who know how to use and, and equally a great disadvantage for those who don't/won't/can't.

The choice of worlds, content, people, faces, language may all have inherent biases that are foisted on users.

Like with the internet or smartphones (or most consumer technology for that matter), I think it will first reduce social inequality from the top, maybe temporarily increasing inequality between those that do and don't have access. But in the long run everyone will benefit.

People create new digital artifacts that are sold for buyers at a market price, but anyone who wants to create digital artifacts themselves can use their own programming skills and imagination to create something new themselves. I think XR will create more social equality than social inequality due to new digital business opportunities that have low entry.

Access will be driven by class and geography and the more business models move in that direction, the more people will be excluded.

If the technology is expensive, lower SES groups will have yet another barrier to face.

It could by being too expensive for many users exacerbate the preexisting socioeconomic disparities that are already severe in many places and between many places in the world.

To start with, there is unequal access to these devices.

Exclusion of those who don't have access to it.

Mainly towards technology illiterate and/or elderly people who will find it difficult to follow

Emerging tech literacy is creating social inequality and different skills access.

Have not thought of any.

Access is an issue - due to hardware cost and educational / technical barrier

Any emerging technology will typically be more accessible to the wealthy, informed and privileged before being more broadly accessible. This will inevitably create inequality. However, in the longer term, XR has the potential to benefit social equality.

Big questions about who owns the XR technology and access to tools.

Content and context of usage can be tailored to few social circles, not intentionally but I'm sure there is some level of unconscious bias embedded in the making

Access to technology can be limited to certain groups due to cost.

There will automatically be a barrier between people who can and cannot afford it.

as explained above.

XR solutions can provide a competitive advantage to users with access to the required technology and applications, XR solutions can be used to target and monitor the environments of specific user groups, people without training may not be able to use XR applications.

Creation of XR solutions is expensive. Thus, such product, services and solution if not heavily subsidized by public agencies, are also going to be expensive. When XR will be available in the market, it will be affordable only for richer people. If XR will be integrated more and more in social lifestyle of people, segregation, and inequality between those who are economically poor and rich will be inevitable.

Like many tech products, XR solutions are available at a range of price points. Smarter solutions will be available to people with more financial freedom than others and could allow them easier access to

information- imagine the difference in someone who can use XR glasses to display contextual information about their environment versus someone who has to move more slowly by using alternative resources for that same information. Furthermore, if XR is incorporated into workforce solutions, job listing preferences such as "comfort with using XR solutions to assist with daily assembly tasks", for example, could lead to exclusion or discouragement for job seekers with less experience to apply. However, I think it is worth noting that XR devices can also allow people with varying abilities to practice skills in safer and more forgiving environments if provided access to the technologies, which would promote social equality- notably, this is based on a condition that those people with varying abilities have access to the technology."

Q35 Please provide examples of job disruption caused by XR solutions

Training actors (for example in the care industry when an actor acts out a certain encounter is now slowly being replaced by a VR training tool).

As used for training, engineering, education, enterprise, construction, medical sectors and more.

I believe disruptions may be caused by digital innovations in general, not XR in particular.

XR is a tool to bring traditional jobs into a new technological age. More people will be able to work from home with XR.

Some jobs will be disrupted but new jobs will be created.

If an XR solution increases the effective work of individual workers, then you can imagine that people will lose jobs since not as many are needed any more.

For existing conventional jobs, it probably has no more impact than advanced video conferencing. However, essentially all technologies of sufficient innovative pressure create around them new industries, and in that space they are definitionally disruptive by virtue of being the foundation of those jobs.

Healthcare sector, especially care such as for mental health, palliative, pain relief, adults with special education needs (SEN).

Currently not, but it may change how people work and interact in the future

More than "disruption" I would rather think about change. How will the jobs change in a more data driven and lazier society?

Spatial Computing has the capability to affect any and every job. Specially, those that are already partially automated.

I would think that digital twins that use XR could somewhat reduce the need for physical mockups.

Hard to say exactly what, but many ways of doing this are already changing due to simple language models like chatGPT, and this will only get amplified as the models evolve and new tech like XR are made available. To me it seems imperative that strict regulations must be in place to ensure that jobs are still around, and the wealth created from automation is redistributed.

Operator roles may change from 'doing' to 'task supervision'.

With effective effectors XR may become the way to "plug in" humans into their jobs remotely.

It makes remote work easier, further reducing the geographic factor for knowledge workers.

The contextual information XR solutions can provide, can make complex jobs more accessible to unskilled or untrained workers."

There is no need for traveling long distances to have in-person meetings with people. XR can create a very realistic feeling environment for people to meet in.

You can fire skilled workers and instead exploit uneducated people with no training, provide poor pay and job conditions and allow them to perform much more advanced tasks just by showing them how to through AR devices. On the other hand, you can greatly enhance the capability of a skilled worker giving them superpowers to do their job better, safer, faster with higher quality. You can also train people very effectively with VR.

It will have an impact on many jobs. Not sure if it will lead to job loss. Probably jobs will change instead.

VR simulations and prototyping, AR on-the-job instructions, remote presence and avatars

AI plus XR and creative industries. XR for training.

I believe the jobs will grow around it if at all there is any impact? There will be a need for skills to develop and design for the technology.

In healthcare nurse that uses only paper-based patient information versus nurse that are able to use digital content by AR XR means.

That's a good thing - we're building the future

Task guidance will make it possible for less skilled workers to perform work that traditionally would have required a higher skill level. This gap can be quite significant, particularly XR combined with AI where AI observes and then provides the discernment of an expert in the act of guiding the unskilled worker.

Replacing/reducing personnel assist installing industrial systems with XR systems to perform installation with reduced personnel.

Automation in general causes loss of jobs whereas in large instances XR is fueled by automation and machine learning!

Remote work and training does change the training and education industry. Also, XR can be used to train robots, leading to loss of jobs due to more automation.

Employers might employ people to work for them from a country where workforce is significantly cheaper

i can only think of positive aspects at the moment, in terms of implementation it facilitates visualization and training. there are negative aspects related to production and socio environmental impacts though.

I see XR as augmenting and not disrupting jobs

Travel and tourism, traditional 2D Movie production technologies, etc."

Q37 Please provide examples related to XR disruptions and impacts on society, economy and environment

Even from the ideation phase, all these factors should be taken into account to really put the audience first and think about their needs and wants for total inclusivity.

Example: facilitating remote work (holograms for telecommunication) will help diminish the use of transportation, but the carbon footprint of XR solutions itself is a problem.

They are all related.

The continuous offering of new devices leads to many unused old devices in the business and privacy domain. Companies should take back old devices and develop proper recycling strategies.

Beyond access, the interactive portions help people transcend their society, economic status, and local environment. For non-virtual applications, the data they collect may help illuminate these impacts on the users of XR technology and empower those users to seek improvement based on demonstrative empirical data they now have in-hand.

Pokemon GO was a social phenomenon that changed not only how people used their phones, but how they moved in the real world. A similar experience with current XR platforms might result in economic development, but also a lot of societal issues.

Giant server farms cost a lot of electricity, and most AR solutions will require heavy server infrastructure to process the image data coming in. This obviously impacts the environment.

Massive expansion of 5G networks that may be useful for some XR applications, making people buy new phones to get 5G connectivity. However, is there even any truth to 5G opening the doors to applications, or would most things work equally well on older network structures? It is likely being constructed anyway, simply because people are buying into the marketing to get them to buy a new phone."

The threshold for automation of most jobs get lower by the day, and we are already seeing wealth and power being consolidated on fewer hands. This is a threat to society, democracy, living standard, and social economic standards. Who will own the freedom of time we might find ourselves with? There are huge opportunities here, but only if we as a people can control the outcome of fewer hands needed.

These things should be considered to ensure any solution does not result in future problems.

XR and digital twins may create a synthetic society, economy, and environment for humanity.

I'm a believer in a mostly free market but would like to make a distinction between the 3 categories. Obviously environmental impact needs to be regulated. Although XR potentially has a positive environmental impact (simulate more / train, travel, use less).

XR supports carbon-free experiences and creates low-entry business opportunities for groups of people who might not have had the equal opportunities to do business in traditional sense.

Societal impacts are crucial to consider when designing and producing XR (and any) technology.

For examples on society, economy etc., see previous examples. For environment one can think of the "tragedy of the commons" tendency when it comes to manufacturing of consumer electronic goods in general where things are not easily repairable, where components that wear down fast are glued and integrated, so it is impossible to replace, and where the sourcing of minerals and other production inputs from the value chain is not transparently disclosed. I could have put this question at 6, but I held back as I think the responsibility should be on governments together with their electorate do figure out and define the rules of the game. One can always encourage commercial players to be responsible but there is a obvious tendency towards race to the bottom spirals and arms races etc., to not lose to your competition that makes it almost impossible for commercial entities to win by acting ethically if the competitive environment isn't regulated to avoid abuses and ethical malpractice. With the right level of regulation and an explicit social contract with the general public one can hope this allows the most ethical players to win in this more advanced and intelligent type of marketplace.

Have not thought of any.

XR, particularly when combined with AI, has the potential to be an equalizer by making it more efficient to train individuals on new skills and making higher paying jobs more accessible to a lower skilled workforce, assuming that the pay would fall somewhere between what that lower skilled worker would be able to do to earn income without XR and what an expert would be able to do and earn. On the other hand, the combination of XR and AI will also eliminate entire categories of work, causing significant labor disruptions

related to the need for large scale retraining combined with a rapid decline in the need for a wide variety of today's jobs and skills. What is yet unknown is whether the pace of creation of new types of jobs, such as AI prompt engineers, can keep pace with job losses.

E-waste, material mining

This is very important. There should be more transdisciplinary exchanges that illuminate the societal impacts of XR. XR is already being adopted by the radical right in various disinformation campaigns and I think we will see this trend growing. I do not think we, as a society, are equipped to deal with this challenge.

Impacts to loss of employment should be taken into consideration as XR has the potential to shift jobs. Long-term sustainment and disposal of XR should be researched and accounted for in life cycle of XR capabilities.

N/A

Raising awareness of climate change, or other crisis can have an impact on society. Digital twins and simulations have an impact of industrial production. Working in 3d space can enhance learning."

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8 Appendix 2: ChatGPT 4 synthesized feedback for each question

Q13

The main user requirements identified in the text, along with their prioritization based on the frequency of occurrences, are as follows:

1. Economic and Geographic Accessibility: The most frequently mentioned issue is the economic barrier to accessing XR technology. This includes the high cost of devices, software, and the lack of necessary infrastructure like 4G/5G or broadband in certain areas. Economic reasons also contribute to the exclusion of people from poorer countries and demographics.
2. Disability and Inclusion: Issues related to disabilities are widely mentioned. This includes challenges for people with visual impairments, motion sickness, and other physical disabilities that make it difficult to use XR technology. The design of XR hardware (like headset straps incompatible with certain hairstyles or headwear) and software also plays a significant role in either excluding or including users with disabilities.
3. Diversity in Representation: This encompasses the low representation of females, indigenous people, and people of color not only in XR content but also in development roles (developers, designers, marketers). There is also a mention of the importance of avatars in XR platforms being customizable to support diverse identities, which ties back to representation.
4. Technical Issues and Accessibility: The sensitivity to lag and latency, as well as the hardware's failure to be universally designed to accommodate various levels of vision, hearing, and motor skills, are mentioned as barriers that exclude users.
5. Language and Age Barriers: Language skills are noted as a barrier to accessing XR, where not speaking English or other major languages can exclude users. Age is also mentioned as a barrier, particularly affecting older individuals who may not have the digital literacy or tech competence to use XR technology effectively.

6. Inclusivity in Content and Professional Use Cases: There is a concern about the inclusivity of content and whether XR applications are being developed with consideration of diverse user groups. This includes professional use cases where XR might be expected to cater to specific groups of people, affecting who is included or excluded.

7. Cultural and Social Considerations: Some issues mentioned involve targeted harassment based on avatar appearance and the need for more culturally sensitive content. This reflects a broader requirement for XR platforms to be mindful of social dynamics and cultural diversity.

These prioritizations reflect the frequency and emphasis placed on each issue within the provided text, indicating areas of user requirement focus in XR technology development.

Q16

To extract and prioritize the main user requirements from the given text regarding avatars in XR (extended reality), I'll first identify distinct user concerns or requirements, then I'll count the frequency of these themes to determine their importance based on occurrences.

Identified Requirements and Themes:

1. Misrepresentation and Manipulation:
 - Posing as someone else (different gender, age, or race) to deceive or harm others.
 - Using avatars to impersonate real or fictional personas for malicious intent.
2. Sexual and Verbal Harassment:
 - Using avatars for sexual harassment or verbal bullying.
 - Grooming, particularly by older users posing as younger.
3. Lack of Personalization and Diversity:
 - Inability to accurately represent oneself due to limited customization options.
 - Need for more racial and gender diversity in avatars.
 - Restrictions in representing non-human avatars or fantasy elements.
4. Identity Theft and Privacy Concerns:
 - Risks associated with identity theft and data protection.
 - Concerns over ethical misuse of avatar identities.
5. Cultural Appropriation and Misrepresentation:
 - Concerns over avatars being used to culturally appropriate or misrepresent groups.
6. Child Safety:
 - Risks of adults posing as children or using child-like avatars to contact minors.
7. Realism and Ethical Issues:
 - Challenges with avatars being too realistic leading to deception or manipulation.
 - Ethical concerns in how avatars are used and perceived in professional or personal settings.
8. Marketing and Deception:
 - Use of avatars for deceptive marketing or as tools in disinformation campaigns.
9. Psychological Impact:
 - The impact of avatars on perception and interaction in digital spaces.

Frequency and Prioritization:

- Misrepresentation and Manipulation (recurring throughout the text with various examples such as gender, age, and racial impersonation).
- Sexual and Verbal Harassment (several mentions of different forms of harassment and abuse).

- Identity Theft and Privacy Concerns (repeatedly addressed through concerns about data protection and identity misuse).
- Lack of Personalization and Diversity (multiple concerns about the lack of options to represent oneself accurately).
- Cultural Appropriation and Misrepresentation (several mentions, including the ethical implications).
- Child Safety (specifically highlighted a few times with concerns about the misuse of child-like avatars).
- Realism and Ethical Issues (noted for their implications on realism in avatars and potential for misuse).
- Marketing and Deception (mentioned in context with misleading marketing practices).
- Psychological Impact (mentioned in the broader context of user interaction).

Based on the frequency and severity of the concerns, the top priorities appear to be addressing Misrepresentation and Manipulation, followed by Sexual and Verbal Harassment, and Identity Theft and Privacy Concerns. These issues are critical as they directly affect user safety and integrity in XR environments.

Q18

Based on the provided text, the main user requirements related to ethical impacts of Generative AI in Extended Reality (XR) can be summarized and prioritized as follows:

1. **Bias and Discrimination:** This is the most frequently mentioned concern, involving how AI systems might amplify existing biases present in their training data, leading to racially and sexually biased outputs. It also covers the risk of bias in programming and AI-based decisions that might not be equitable or fair.
2. **Misinformation and Disinformation:** The ability of Generative AI to create and spread false information, including manipulation of public opinion, is a significant ethical concern. This includes the generation of content that could mislead, such as fake news, stereotypes, and other forms of misinformation.
3. **Identity and Privacy Issues:** Concerns include identity theft, fraud, and the creation of fake identities or avatars that mimic real people without their consent. It also encompasses the broader implications for privacy, especially in terms of how personal data might be used without users' knowledge or consent.
4. **Intellectual Property Violations:** This includes the unauthorized use of copyrighted or creative content without permission or compensation to the original creators. Concerns were also raised about the potential for AI to "steal" the artistic outputs or the unique look and feel created by individuals.
5. **Psychological Impact:** The potential for AI to psychologically manipulate users through personalized and highly realistic interactions was noted. This includes creating scenarios or avatars that can deeply influence personal beliefs or emotions.
6. **Authenticity of Information:** This relates to the concern about AI's capacity to generate ethically questionable content based on biased or flawed input data, leading to outputs that may not be authentic or true.
7. **Cultural Misrepresentation:** The potential for AI to misrepresent or inaccurately portray cultural elements due to skewed or culturally homogeneous training data.
8. **Regulatory and Ethical Maturity:** The need for Generative AI technology, especially in XR, to mature ethically and be subject to appropriate regulation before being widely adopted. This includes a balanced approach to innovation and creativity versus ethical implications.

These priorities reflect the frequency and seriousness of concerns mentioned in the text, with bias and misinformation being the most critical due to their potential for widespread and systemic impacts.

Q20

To extract and prioritize user requirements from the provided text based on occurrences, we first need to identify the main security concerns and ethical issues in XR (Extended Reality) that are mentioned. Here's a breakdown of each, followed by a prioritization based on frequency and implied severity:

Security Concerns in XR

1. **Personal Data Security and Privacy:** Concerns about companies selling personal data to third parties, especially related to advertising and tracking biometric data via head-mounted displays (HMDs) without clear information on data usage. This includes facial recognition, voice, and even emotional responses captured and possibly misused.
2. **Physical Safety:** Issues such as distractions from real-world dangers while engaged in XR environments, exemplified by accidents involving Pokémon GO players or potential hazards when using devices like Apple Vision Pro in inappropriate settings.
3. **Platform and Developer Security Practices:** The need for secure APIs for VR game modding communities to limit access to user information while enabling user participation. This also covers the security vulnerabilities inherent in cloud-based systems that improperly handle data, particularly across national borders.
4. **Security of Digital Environments:** Concerns about creating secure digital twins and the implications of digital vs. physical security measures. This includes securing XR environments in sectors like healthcare and defense where the stakes are particularly high.
5. **Data Storage and Access Control:** Storing data on devices and the potential misuse of this data. Also concerns about the accessibility and security of XR devices and software, including issues with adding accounts or using devices across different users.

Ethical Issues in XR

1. **Consent and Awareness:** The challenge of users entering XR experiences without full knowledge of what they are consenting to, which raises concerns about the ethical use of data and the representation of sensitive historical or personal content.
2. **Data Privacy and Biometrics:** Concerns over the use of biometric data for targeting and inference, particularly related to sensitive characteristics or medical conditions. This extends to the broader concern of ethical data use and privacy.
3. **Manipulation and Autonomy:** Issues related to the manipulation of user behavior and autonomy, specifically through game mechanics in apps like Pokémon GO or through other commercially driven incentives that may exploit users.
4. **Representation and Accessibility:** Ethical considerations around the representation of different demographics in XR and ensuring accessibility to diverse user groups.
5. **Research Ethics and Corporate Responsibility:** The role of corporate ethics, diversity, and inclusion in developing and deploying XR technologies, especially in terms of research ethics and the governance of data use and application.

Prioritization of Concerns

- **Data Security and Privacy (both in security and ethical contexts):** Most frequently mentioned and carries significant implications for user trust and safety.
- **Physical Safety and Security Practices:** Critical due to the direct impact on user safety and the broader implications for public trust in XR technologies.

- Consent and Awareness: Central to ethical discussions, particularly in terms of user empowerment and respect in the digital sphere.
- Platform Security and Developer Practices: Essential for building a secure and sustainable XR ecosystem that supports both creators and users.
- Representation and Accessibility: Important for ensuring that XR technologies are inclusive and ethically sound.

These priorities reflect both the frequency of mentions in the text and the potential impact these issues could have on users and society.

Q22

To extract and prioritize the main user requirements regarding ethical issues in XR (extended reality), I'll summarize and count the specific concerns mentioned in the text. Here's a prioritized list based on their occurrences and implications:

1. Privacy and Data Security:
 - Concerns about biometrics and privacy issues related to facial recognition and other tracking technologies in augmented reality, virtual reality, and head-mounted displays.
 - Use of data related to personal information in ways that may not be ethical or are under-regulated (mentioned in the context of GDPR and general research ethics).
 - Concerns about unethical data use, even though it's not personally experienced, there's a general suspicion it's happening.
2. Consent and User Awareness:
 - Issues related to users going into XR experiences without full knowledge or understanding of what they are consenting to.
 - Concerns about manipulation through game mechanics, as in the example of Pokemon Go, where users are nudged to specific locations without clear communication that their behavior is being manipulated for commercial interests.
3. Representation and Respect:
 - Ethical considerations in how Holocaust survivors are represented in VR, particularly how volumetric video assets are managed and manipulated.
 - Inadequate representation of avatars that could affect understanding and analysis of complex tasks across different user demographics.
4. Ethical Practices in Development and Research:
 - Importance of ethics, diversity, and inclusion in the development and governance of XR technologies, with a focus on pre-release phases.
 - Conflicts of interest between public and private research interests and the implications for user safety.
5. Accessibility and Inclusion:
 - Issues with the accessibility of XR technologies for certain groups, particularly in experimental or moral lab settings.
 - Use of anthropometric data which may exclude individuals from fully engaging with or benefiting from XR technologies.
6. Commercial and Geographic Ethical Concerns:

- Ethical concerns in specific geographic regions or industry areas where there is a low diversity of ethical perspectives.
- Challenges related to the commercial exploitation of XR technologies and the broader impact on societal norms and individual autonomy.

These priorities highlight a spectrum of ethical considerations ranging from individual privacy and informed consent to broader societal impacts and the governance of XR technology development. Each of these areas presents critical challenges that require thoughtful consideration and proactive management by stakeholders in the XR field.

Q26

From the provided text, several key user requirements and concerns related to the use of Extended Reality (XR) technologies emerge. Here are the main points extracted and prioritized based on their frequency of mention and implied importance:

1. Privacy and Data Security:
 - Misuse of Personal Data: Concerns about the continuous capture and processing of personal data for advertising, profiling, and manipulation by private entities and AI systems.
 - Surveillance and Monitoring: Issues related to constant monitoring of location, behavior, and even biometric data which can lead to control over user behaviors and decisions.
2. Autonomy and Personal Freedom:
 - Influence and Manipulation: Worries about the potential for XR to manipulate user perceptions, beliefs, and decisions, including through biased views and fake news, which can fundamentally alter one's understanding of reality and social dynamics.
 - Restrictions through Technology: Concerns that XR platforms can limit user autonomy by locking key features behind paywalls, creating dependency, or by the nature of the technology itself limiting real-world freedoms.
3. Ethical Use and Regulation:
 - Potential for Abuse: The potential misuse of XR by commercial interests, employers, and other actors to exploit users or manipulate their experiences and choices.
 - Lack of Regulation: Calls for stricter regulatory oversight to prevent unethical practices, including the manipulation of user agency and the intensive capturing of user attention for profit.
4. Equity and Accessibility:
 - Exclusion and Accessibility Issues: Concerns that XR technologies may exclude certain users based on social, economic, or physical limitations. Discussions about XR's potential to provide more inclusive experiences for people with disabilities but also concerns about creating new barriers for others.
5. Impact on Perception and Decision-Making:
 - Changing Perceptions: Fears about how XR can alter one's perception of reality, politics, and self, often referred to as "epistemic security."
 - Decision-Making Influence: Concerns that the ability to delay or avoid decisions through XR technologies might diminish personal agency and self-management.
6. Positive Applications:
 - Benefits in Healthcare and Training: Acknowledgement of the potential positive impacts of XR on training, mental health support, and enhancing the social capabilities of individuals who struggle with traditional social settings.

These requirements and concerns highlight a mix of excitement for the potential benefits of XR and apprehension about its risks, particularly regarding privacy, autonomy, and ethical use. Addressing these effectively will be crucial for the responsible development and adoption of XR technologies.

Q28

- From the provided text, several key user requirements related to privacy infringement and freedom of expression in Extended Reality (XR) can be extracted and prioritized based on their frequency and importance:
 - Privacy Concerns:
 - Data Usage Without Consent: Multiple instances mention concerns about collecting and using personal data without user consent, especially regarding personal safety and privacy.
 - Surveillance and Data Storage: Concerns about surveillance, recording of daily actions, and the use of stored data for purposes not transparent or agreed upon by the user (e.g., advertising, employer monitoring).
 - 1. Freedom of Expression:
 - Censorship and Content Moderation: Numerous references to issues with censorship, content filtering, banning, and limitations on what users can express or access on platforms.
 - Platform Control and Limited Alternatives: Concerns about large, centralized platforms limiting expression due to few viable alternatives and the possibility of totalitarian control over expression, particularly in regimes or large tech ecosystems.
 - 2. Chilling Effect of Surveillance:
 - Restricting Speech Based on Jurisdiction: Issues with speech being restricted based on geographic or political jurisdiction, including targeting specific forms of expression by state actors.
 - Surveillance Impact on Expression: The effect of surveillance on limiting freedom of expression, making users wary of what they express due to potential monitoring.
 - 3. Lack of Representation and Personal Expression:
 - Avatar Representation: Variability in avatar representation across platforms affecting personal expression, such as lack of choice in body shape, binary gender representation, and religious suppression.
 - 4. Ethical and Societal Implications:
 - Impact of Ethics on Expression: Concerns about how ethical conditioning in generative AI and other technologies might restrict freedom of expression.
 - Awareness and Self-Censorship: How increased awareness of XR's capabilities might lead users to self-censor or restrict their expression due to privacy concerns.

These requirements reveal a deep concern for both privacy and the right to freely express oneself without undue restriction or surveillance, especially in the context of powerful, centralizing technologies like XR. There is a clear call for more robust privacy protections, transparent data practices, and greater diversity in platform options to support free expression.

Q30

To extract and prioritize the main user requirements related to human rights concerns in XR (Extended Reality), we'll identify the recurring themes from the text and count their occurrences:

1. Awareness and Empathy for Human Rights Violations:
 - Using XR to raise awareness about human trafficking, domestic abuse, female genital mutilation, migration, and other human rights issues.
 - Showcasing when human rights have been taken from someone or a group to build empathy.
 - Count: 2 (Both are about using XR positively for raising awareness and empathy).
2. Potential Misuse of XR:
 - Concerns about using XR tools for negative outcomes like propaganda or showcasing evil.
 - The use of XR for propaganda in Russia, especially in a museum in occupied Ukrainian territories.
 - Count: 2 (Mentioned in the context of both positive and negative effects).
3. Privacy and Surveillance:
 - Concerns about XR headsets becoming tools for mass surveillance due to uncontrolled hardware-level access to sensors like microphones and cameras.
 - Count: 1
4. Inappropriate Content and Experiences:
 - Experiencing a concentration camp scenario in VR being considered a violation of human rights.
 - Instances of sexual assault, hate speech, and bullying related to XR.
 - Count: 2 (These points deal with inappropriate or harmful content).
5. Censorship and Freedom of Speech:
 - Concerns about censorship and infringement on freedom of speech based on the biases of big tech companies and political cultures.
 - Count: 1
6. Accessibility and Compliance with ADA:
 - Few XR solutions meet basic ADA (American Disabilities Act) requirements, especially concerning accessibility for visually impaired users.
 - Count: 1

Prioritizing based on occurrences:

1. Awareness and Empathy for Human Rights Violations - Most frequently mentioned as a positive application of XR to combat and educate on human rights issues.
2. Inappropriate Content and Experiences - Similarly emphasized, with a focus on ensuring XR does not foster environments where harmful content is experienced.
3. Potential Misuse of XR - Significant concerns about using XR in propagating false narratives or misuse in sensitive geopolitical contexts.
4. Privacy and Surveillance - Important due to the inherent risks of technology in invading personal privacy without adequate controls.

5. Censorship and Freedom of Speech - A specific but critical issue regarding how XR platforms are managed and the cultural impacts on content moderation.
6. Accessibility and Compliance with ADA - Essential for making XR accessible to all users, highlighting the need for inclusive design.

These priorities highlight the need to develop XR technologies responsibly, considering both their potential for positive impact and risks of misuse or harmful effects.

Q 33

Based on the provided text, here are the main user requirements concerning social inequality in XR (Extended Reality), prioritized by their frequency of occurrence:

1. Cost and Accessibility:
 - Cost is a significant barrier, making XR inaccessible to lower socio-economic groups.
 - High equipment standards and associated costs prevent access for many, exacerbating the digital divide.
 - The need for expensive devices and possibly fast internet connections like 5G limits access to wealthy users and regions.
2. Digital Literacy and Technical Competence:
 - Digital illiteracy is a growing issue, especially in economically poorer areas, and XR might not be accessible to those who lack technological skills.
 - XR might increase the divide between tech-savvy individuals and those who are technology illiterate or elderly.
3. Exclusivity and Bias in Content Creation:
 - A noted imbalance in VR experiences, primarily created by and for males.
 - Content and context might cater to specific social circles, potentially carrying unconscious biases.
 - The creation of XR solutions and content may not be inclusive or democratized, leading to a narrower range of perspectives and experiences.
4. Equity and Inclusivity in Usage and Access:
 - Inequalities observed in platforms like VRChat based on user status or subscription levels.
 - Disparities in who can afford and access the latest technologies, which may leave others behind.
 - Emerging tech literacy and access to tools are uneven, favoring those who are already privileged.
5. Long-term Impact on Social Equality:
 - While some believe XR will ultimately reduce social inequality by providing more access and connectivity, there are concerns about its initial impact in deepening existing disparities.
 - There are big questions about who owns the technology and who has access to these tools, indicating potential long-term implications for social structures.
6. Integration and Adoption Challenges:
 - Concerns about the slow adoption among specific groups due to costs, lack of resources, or reluctance to embrace new technologies.
 - Potential for XR to provide competitive advantages, which could further segregate user groups based on access to technology.

These requirements reflect concerns about the broad availability of XR technologies, their affordability, the inclusivity of their content, and the broader social impacts of their integration into daily life. Addressing these issues is crucial for ensuring that XR contributes positively to reducing social inequality rather than exacerbating it.

Q35

To extract and prioritize the main user requirements regarding the impact of XR (Extended Reality) solutions on jobs from the provided text, I will list the various impacts mentioned and count their occurrences to determine their priority:

1. **Training and Education:** XR technologies are frequently mentioned as tools for enhancing training and education, especially using VR for simulations and providing on-the-job AR instructions. This is highlighted across sectors like healthcare, engineering, and education.
2. **Remote Work Enhancements:** Several instances in the text discuss how XR facilitates remote work, making geographical location less significant and enabling more people to work from home.
3. **Job Role Transformation and Creation:** The text reflects on how XR may transform existing jobs and create new ones, particularly through the integration of XR with other technologies like AI, which can guide less skilled workers or replace traditional job functions.
4. **Job Disruption and Reduction:** Concerns are raised about XR potentially leading to job losses as the technology might allow fewer workers to achieve more or replace the need for certain job roles altogether.
5. **Healthcare Sector Impact:** Specific mentions of XR applications in healthcare, such as mental health, palliative care, and special education needs, indicate a significant impact on this sector.
6. **Accessibility for Unskilled Workers:** XR can make complex jobs more accessible to unskilled or untrained workers by providing contextual information and task guidance, potentially lowering training requirements.
7. **Reduction in Physical Presence Needs:** XR reduces the need for physical travel and presence, as it can simulate realistic environments for meetings and interactions.
8. **Digital and Spatial Computing Impact:** The text notes that XR, combined with digital and spatial computing, could affect nearly every job sector, particularly those already seeing automation.
9. **Regulation and Social Implications:** There are calls for regulations to ensure that jobs are preserved, and the wealth generated from automation is fairly distributed, reflecting a concern for the broader social impact of XR.
10. **Industrial and Production Changes:** XR's application in industrial settings for tasks like system installation and prototyping is also highlighted.
11. **Travel and Tourism, Movie Production:** XR's potential effects on traditional sectors like travel, tourism, and traditional movie production are mentioned as areas of disruption.

By counting these themes from the text and their occurrences, the top priorities appear to be training and education, remote work enhancements, and job role transformation and creation, as these are the most frequently mentioned impacts of XR solutions. These priorities suggest a focus on how XR can be integrated into workforce development and operational transformations in various industries.

Q37

The user requirements from the text provided can be grouped and prioritized based on their frequency and significance. Here are the main requirements identified:

1. **Environmental Impact Considerations:** The need to consider the environmental impact of XR technologies appears repeatedly, focusing on factors like e-waste, energy consumption of server

farms, and the lifecycle of XR devices. This includes the call for responsible recycling strategies and regulation of environmental impacts.

2. **Societal Impacts:** The text emphasizes the importance of addressing the societal impacts of XR, such as privacy concerns, the potential for disinformation campaigns, and the social dynamics changed by XR technologies like those observed with Pokémon GO.
3. **Economic Impacts and Accessibility:** There are several mentions of economic impacts and accessibility, including the creation of low-entry business opportunities and the effects on job markets due to automation and new job creation. The text also questions the economic viability and necessity of technology like 5G in relation to XR.
4. **Technology Life Cycle Management:** Managing the life cycle of XR technologies, including recycling and proper disposal, is highlighted to avoid long-term environmental and societal issues.
5. **Equitable Access and Opportunities:** Ensuring that XR technologies provide equal opportunities for all individuals, particularly in terms of job accessibility and training capabilities, is a stated requirement.
6. **Regulation and Ethical Considerations:** The need for appropriate regulation to manage the impacts of XR and to ensure ethical practices in its deployment and operation is mentioned. This includes the interplay of government and commercial interests in shaping the future of XR.
7. **Impact on Infrastructure and Resource Use:** References to the infrastructure demands of XR, like server farms and 5G networks, and the associated resource use and economic implications are noted.
8. **Empirical Data Use and Transparency:** The importance of using empirical data to understand and improve the impacts of XR, along with calls for transparency in the manufacturing and sourcing of XR components.

These requirements can be prioritized based on their occurrence and the breadth of impact they might have:

1. Environmental Impact Considerations (most frequently mentioned and wide-reaching impacts)
2. Societal Impacts (critical for maintaining social structure and trust)
3. Economic Impacts and Accessibility (significant for ensuring the broad and beneficial deployment of XR)
4. Regulation and Ethical Considerations (essential for sustainable and ethical practice)
5. Technology Life Cycle Management (important for environmental and social sustainability)
6. Equitable Access and Opportunities (key to leveraging XR as an equalizer in society)
7. Impact on Infrastructure and Resource Use (important but more specific to certain XR applications)
8. Empirical Data Use and Transparency (foundational for informed decision-making and policy)

These prioritizations can guide the development and deployment of XR technologies to maximize positive outcomes and minimize potential negative impacts.

9 Appendix 3: ChatGPT 4 raw feedback synthesized from all questions

Based on the provided text, the main user requirements related to equal representation or exclusion in XR can be extracted and prioritized as follows:

1. ****Economic Accessibility and Socioeconomic Factors****: The most frequently mentioned concern is the affordability of XR technology and the economic barriers preventing access. This includes the cost of devices, software, and the necessary connectivity infrastructure (e.g., 4G/5G), which can exclude economically disadvantaged individuals and regions.
2. ****Disabilities and Physical Limitations****: Another significant concern is the exclusion of people with disabilities. Issues such as compatibility with various physical disabilities (e.g., vision impairment, motion sickness), the design of XR headsets not accommodating different hairstyles or head wear, and the broader need for universally designed solutions that are accessible to all are highlighted multiple times.
3. ****Representation of Diverse Identities****: The text frequently addresses the lack of representation and inclusion of various identities in XR content and development. This includes underrepresentation of women, people of color, and indigenous groups both as users and creators in the XR space. Also, there is a call for better avatar customization to reflect diverse identities.
4. ****Geographic Limitations****: Limited internet access and the availability of XR technology in certain geographic regions are mentioned as barriers. This can lead to exclusion based on where one lives, further compounding social and economic disparities.
5. ****Age and Tech Literacy****: Age-related barriers and the digital divide are noted concerns, particularly affecting older populations' ability to engage with XR technologies due to unfamiliarity or physical limitations related to aging.
6. ****Gender Inequality****: Specific to funding and development opportunities in XR, there is a notable mention of gender inequality affecting the availability of resources and support for projects led by or intended for women.

These requirements highlight a range of user concerns that need addressing in the development and deployment of XR technologies, with economic and physical accessibility at the forefront. These should be prioritized to ensure XR technologies are inclusive and equitable.

The text provided highlights several key user requirements related to XR (Extended Reality) experiences. These requirements focus on inclusion, accessibility, and the broader societal and economic implications of XR technology. Here's a prioritized list based on the frequency and emphasis of occurrences in the text:

1. **Accessibility and Inclusivity**:
 - **Physical Compatibility**: Adjustments needed for XR headsets to accommodate different hairstyles and head wear like braids, Afros, turbans, etc.
 - **Visual Disabilities**: Inclusion of people with visual impairments, including concerns about XR applications that require visual perception which may exclude users with reduced or no vision.
 - **Digital Literacy and Age**: Addressing the barriers faced by older individuals or those lacking digital skills in using XR technologies.
2. **Economic and Geographic Accessibility**:
 - **Cost of Technology**: The high cost of XR devices and technology which could exclude economically disadvantaged users and poorer countries.

- **Geographic Disparities:** Limited internet access or the unavailability of advanced network infrastructure like 4G/5G in some regions, hindering access to XR.
- 3. **Cultural and Demographic Representation:**
 - **Gender and Ethnic Diversity:** Ensuring fair representation within development teams and in XR content. This includes targeted efforts to include women and people of color in development roles.
 - **Cultural Appropriation and Sensitivity:** Addressing concerns related to the proper representation of cultures, avoiding stereotypes, and ensuring that XR content does not inadvertently perpetuate cultural insensitivity.
- 4. **Socioeconomic Factors:**
 - **Employment and Skill Displacement:** Concerns about XR replacing traditional jobs and the need for retraining and adapting the workforce to leverage XR technologies.
 - **Language Barriers:** Ensuring XR technologies are accessible to non-English speakers and those who speak various international languages.
- 5. **Ethical and Safety Concerns:**
 - **Privacy and Data Security:** Addressing how XR collects and uses personal data, ensuring robust security measures to protect user information.
 - **Mental and Physical Health:** Considerations for the potential strain on mental health and risks like motion sickness associated with prolonged use of XR.
- 6. **Technical Challenges and User Experience:**
 - **Interoperability and Customization:** Ensuring XR platforms support customizable avatars and inclusive content creation tools to cater to diverse user needs.
 - **Hardware Design:** Improvements in the design of XR headsets to be more accommodating of different physical features and needs.

These priorities reflect the critical areas that need attention to make XR technologies more accessible, equitable, and beneficial to a broader spectrum of society.

10 Appendix 4: User requirements concept map

Figure 11: Example of user requirements concept map

11 Appendix 5: Survey Questionnaire

- Q1. Please click to indicate that you understand and agree to these statements and consent to take part.
- I understand that confidentiality will be maintained and that my email address, if provided, will not be shared with any other parties
 - I understand that anonymized results from this survey may be disseminated through project reports, conference presentations, peer-reviewed journals, used in future projects, included on institutional websites and made available on online data repositories
 - I understand that my email address, if provided, will not be linked with the research material, and I will not be identifiable in the reports that result from the research
 - I understand that if I choose to withdraw my data by contacting the XR4Human consortium by June 30, 2024, my responses will be removed from the dataset and will not be used in the analysis
 - I understand that I am free to withdraw at any time without giving any reason and without any consequences
 - I have read and understood the information on the survey presented above and have been offered the opportunity to clarify by contacting the XR4Human consortium (<https://xr4human.eu/#contact>)
 - I agree to take part in this survey
- Q2. Please provide your email address (optional)
- Q3. Please identify yourself with one or several of the following stakeholder categories
- Q4. My involvement in XR
- Q5. Gender
- Q6. Your age group
- Q7. Country of residence
- Q8. How important is the privacy of personal data collected by XR applications and devices for you personally? (1 = do not know, 2 = LOW, 6 = VERY HIGH)
- Q9. How important is the privacy of personal data collected by XR applications and devices for you professionally? (1 = do not know, 2 = LOW, 6 = VERY HIGH)
- Q10. How important is it that XR solution providers obtain explicit consent from users before collecting their data? (1 = do not know, 2 = LOW, 6 = VERY HIGH)
- Q11. Have you experienced a lack of equal representation of various cultures, ethnicities, and demographics in XR solutions? (1 = do not know, 2 = LOW, 6 = VERY HIGH)
- Q12. To what extent could XR solutions exclude certain groups? (1 = do not know, 2 = LOW, 6 = VERY HIGH)
- Q13. Please provide examples related to equal representation or exclusion in XR (optional)
- Q14. How important are Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion (DEI) in XR solutions (1 = do not know, 2 = LOW, 6 = VERY HIGH)

- Q15. To what extent do you think that avatars could contribute to manipulation and misrepresentation in XR solutions (1 = do not know, 2 = LOW, 6 = VERY HIGH)
- Q16. Please provide examples related to manipulation and misrepresentation using avatars in XR (optional)
- Q17. To what extent do you think Generative AI in XR solutions impacts ethics (1 = do not know, 2 = LOW, 6 = VERY HIGH)
- Q18. Please provide examples related to ethical impacts of Generative AI in XR (optional)
- Q19. To what extent have you encountered XR solutions that raised security concerns? (1 = do not know, 2 = LOW, 6 = VERY HIGH)
- Q20. Please provide examples related to security in XR (optional)
- Q21. To what extent have you or your organization encountered ethical issues related to data use in XR solutions? (1 = do not know, 2 = LOW, 6 = VERY HIGH)
- Q22. Please provide examples related to ethical issues in XR (optional)
- Q23. To what extent are you aware of ethics industry standards or best practices for data usage in XR solutions? (1 = do not know, 2 = LOW, 6 = VERY HIGH)
- Q24. How confident are you in the ability of current regulations to protect user data in the context of XR solutions? (1 = do not know, 2 = LOW, 6 = VERY HIGH)
- Q25. To what extent do you believe XR solutions may impact an individual's autonomy and personal freedoms? (1 = do not know, 2 = LOW, 6 = VERY HIGH)
- Q26. Please provide examples related to autonomy and personal freedom in XR (optional)
- Q27. How concerned are you about the potential for XR solutions to infringe on privacy and freedom of expression? (1 = do not know, 2 = LOW, 6 = VERY HIGH)
- Q28. Please provide examples related to privacy infringement and freedom of expression in XR (optional)
- Q29. Have you encountered cases where XR solutions raised human rights concerns? (1 = do not know, 2 = LOW, 6 = VERY HIGH)
- Q30. Please provide examples related to human rights concerns in XR (optional)
- Q31. How strongly do you believe that there is a need for ethical guidelines specifically addressing human rights issues in XR development? (1 = do not know, 2 = LOW, 6 = VERY HIGH)
- Q32. To what extent do you think that XR solutions may create social inequality? (1 = do not know, 2 = LOW, 6 = VERY HIGH)
- Q33. Please provide examples related to social inequality in XR (optional)
- Q34. To what extent do you believe that XR technology has the potential to disrupt traditional jobs? (1 = do not know, 2 = LOW, 6 = VERY HIGH)
- Q35. Please provide examples of job disruption caused by XR solutions (optional)

- Q36. To what extent should XR solution providers take into account societal, economic, and environmental impacts alongside technological innovation? (1 = do not know, 2 = LOW, 6 = VERY HIGH)
- Q37. Please provide examples related to XR disruptions and impacts on society, economy and environment (optional)
- Q38. How do you seek information about ethics related to XR?

This deliverable is awaiting approval from the European Commission